

Algebraic Double-Digit and Cornered Magic Squares of Odd Orders from 5 to 19

The whole work is also available at author's sites:
<https://numbers-magic.com/?p=17179>

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Abstract

This work brings **double-digit** or **double-layer algebraic** magic squares of odd orders from 5 to 19 for reduced entries. This study include three types of algebraic magic squares, i.e., **cyclic-type**, **flat-type** and **corner-type**. The **cyclic-type** and the **flat-type** are two different ways of writing **double-digit** magic squares. In this work, we always use **magic rectangles** of width 2 except in the middle or corner, where there are magic squares of order 3 or 5. The idea of **double-digit** and **cornered** magic squares for sequential entries is already studied by the authors. For details refer the author's work on **double-digit** [23, 31, 25, 26, 27, 28, 29] and **cornered** [30, 31, 32, 33, 34, 35, 36]. Combing three works of author [37, 38, 39], we have **algebraic magic squares** of even and odd orders from 4 to 20. It includes, **double-digits**, **cornered** and **striped** magic squares. For similar kind of work for different orders in different styles and designs, the readers are suggested to see author's work [13, 14, 15, 16, 17, 18, 19, 20, 21].

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1 Introduction

This work brings **double-digit** or **double-layer algebraic** magic squares of odd orders from 5 to 19 for reduced entries. This study include three types of algebraic magic squares, i.e., **cyclic-type**, **flat-type** and **corner-type**. **Cyclic-type** and **flat-type** are two different ways of writing as **double-digit** magic squares. In this work, we always use **magic rectangles** of width 2 except in the middle or corner, where there is a magic square of order 3 or 5. The idea of **double-digit** and **cornered** magic squares for sequential entries is already studied by the authors. For details see the reference lists given at the end of this work.

We know that magic sum of a magic square of order n having 1 to n^2 number of entries is given by

$$S_{n \times n} := \frac{n \times (1 + n^2)}{2}$$

By algebraic magic squares we understand that the entries of a magic square are **variables** and their combinations. Instead of **sequential** entries, we have **non-sequential** entries. These can be positive, negative or decimal numbers.

Summarizing, this work brings **double-digit** or **double-layer algebraic** magic squares of odd orders from 5 to 19 for **reduced entries**. Sometimes, these types of magic squares, we call as **self-made**, because they are complete in themselves. Just choose the entries and magic sum, we always get a magic square.

The idea of **double-digit** for magic squares for **sequential** entries is studied by the author [29] for the first time. This work is for **non-sequential** entries. Moreover, we have considered the magic rectangles in a **cyclic**, **flat** or **cornered** way. For similar kind of work for different orders in different styles and ways, the readers are suggested to see author's work [13, 14, 15, 16, 17, 18, 19, 20, 21]. For **double-digit** work for **sequential** entries refer [23, 24, 25, 26, 27, 28, 29].

Combing all the three works appearing [37, 38, 39], finally, we have **algebraic magic squares** of even and odd orders from 4 to 20. It includes, **double-digits**, **cornered** and **striped** magic squares.

2 Double-Digit Algebraic Striped Magic Squares

The section bring results and examples of **reduced entries algebraic** magic squares complete in itself for odd orders from 5 to 19. These are of three types: **cyclic**, **flat** and **corner**. From order 7 onwards there are three different ways of writing different magic squares in each case.

2.1 Double-Digit Algebraic Magic Square of Order 5

2.1.1 Cornered

Result 2.1. *An algebraic cornered magic square of order 5 is given by*

$a1+a2-S/3$	$2*S/3-a2$	$2*S/3-a1$	$2*S/3-a3$	$a3$
$4*S/3-2*a1-a2$	$S/3$	$2*a1+a2-2*S/3$	$2*S/3-a4$	$a4$
$a1$	$a2$	$S-a1-a2$	$a3+a4-(1/3)*S$	$S-a3-a4$
$(4/3)*S+a3-a4-a1-a2-a5$	$2*S/3-a5$	$a4+a1+a2+2*a5+2*a6-(5/3)*S-a3$	$2*S/3-a6$	$2*S/3-a6$
$a4+a1+a2+a5-(2/3)*S-a3$	$a5$	$(7/3)*S+a3-a4-a1-a2-2*a5-2*a6$	$a6$	$a6$

• **Details**

It is an **algebraic cornered** magic square of order 5 composed of two magic rectangles of orders 2×5 and 2×5 . In this case, the magic sums are $S_{3 \times 3} := S$ and $S_{5 \times 5} := \frac{5S}{3}$. The width of magic rectangles is given as $m := \frac{2S}{3}$. In order to avoid decimal entries the magic sum of order 3 should be multiple of 3. Below are two examples.

Example 2.1. Let's consider following two examples based on the Result 2.1:

5	mgc				45		5	mgc				55	
	14	5	8	2	16	45		12	9	12	6	16	55
	3	9	15	-1	19	45		11	11	11	3	19	55
	10	13	4	26	-8	45		10	13	10	24	-2	55
	-12	-4	75	-7	-7	45		-4	0	65	-3	-3	55
	30	22	-57	25	25	45		26	22	-43	25	25	55
	45	45	45	45	45	45		55	55	55	55	55	55

The magic sums are:

- **First example:** $S_{3 \times 3} := 30, S_{5 \times 5} := 45$ and $m := 18$.
- **Second example:** $S_{3 \times 3} := 33, S_{5 \times 5} := 55$ and $m := 22$.

There are few more types of **algebraic** magic squares of order 5. For details refer Taneja [13, 15].

2.2 Double-Digit Algebraic Magic Squares of Order 7

Below are three different ways of writing magic square of order 7, i.e., **cyclic**, **flat** and **cornered**.

2.2.1 Cyclic-Type

Result 2.2. Let's consider an *algebraic* magic square of order 7 with *reduced entries*:

a3	a4	a5	a6	$(5/3)*S-a3-a4-a5-a6$	$(2/3)*S-a7$	a7
$(2/3)*S-a3$	$(2/3)*S-a4$	$(2/3)*S-a5$	$(2/3)*S-a6$	$a3+a4+a5+a6-S$	$(2/3)*S-a8$	a8
$(5/3)*S+a7-a8-2*a14-a15-a16$	$a8+2*a14+a15+a16-S-a7$	$a1+a2-S/3$	$2*S/3-a2$	$2*S/3-a1$	$(2/3)*S-a9$	a9
a16	$(2/3)*S-a16$	$4*S/3-2*a1-a2$	$S/3$	$2*a1+a2-2*S/3$	$(2/3)*S-a10$	a10
a15	$(2/3)*S-a15$	a1	a2	$S-a1-a2$	$a7+a8+a9+a10-S$	$(5/3)*S-a7-a8-a9-a10$
a14	$(2/3)*S-a14$	$a4+2*a11+a12+a13-S-a3$	$(2/3)*S-a13$	$(2/3)*S-a12$	$(2/3)*S-a11$	$(2/3)*S+a3-a4-a11$
$a8+a14-a7$	$(2/3)*S+a7-a8-a14$	$(5/3)*S+a3-a4-2*a11-a12-a13$	a13	a12	a11	$a4+a11-a3$

• Details

It is an *algebraic* magic square of order 7 composed of four equal sums magic rectangles of orders 2×5 and embedded with a magic square of order 3. Since the external four strips are of equal sums, we can name it is as an *algebraic cyclic-type* magic square of order 7. In this case, the magic sums are $S_{3 \times 3} := S$ and $S_{7 \times 7} := \frac{7S}{3}$. The width of magic rectangles is given as $m := \frac{2S}{3}$. In order to avoid decimal entries the magic sum of order 3 should be multiple of 3. Below are two examples.

Example 2.2. Let's consider following two examples based on the Result 2.2:

7	mgc							49	7	mgc								56
	12	13	14	15	-19	-2	16	49		12	13	14	15	-14	0	16		56
	2	1	0	-1	33	-3	17	49		4	3	2	1	30	-1	17		56
	-61	75	14	3	4	-4	18	49		-56	72	13	5	6	-2	18		56
	25	-11	-3	7	17	-5	19	49		25	-9	1	8	15	-3	19		56
	24	-10	10	11	0	49	-35	49		24	-8	10	11	3	46	-30		56
	23	-9	63	-8	-7	-6	-7	49		23	-7	60	-6	-5	-4	-5		56
	24	-10	-49	22	21	20	21	49		24	-8	-44	22	21	20	21		56
	49	49	49	49	49	49	49	49		56	56	56	56	56	56	56		56

The magic sums are:

- **First example:** $S_{3 \times 3} := 21, S_{7 \times 7} := 49$ and $m := 14$.
- **Second example:** $S_{3 \times 3} := 24, S_{7 \times 7} := 56$ and $m := 16$.

2.2.2 Flat-Type

Result 2.3. Let's consider an *algebraic magic square of order 7 with reduced entries*:

a3	a4	a5	a6	$(7/3)*S-a3-a4-a5-a6-a7-a8$	a7	a8
$(2/3)*S-a3$	$(2/3)*S-a4$	$(2/3)*S-a5$	$(2/3)*S-a6$	$a3+a4+a5+a6+a7+a8-(5/3)*S$	$(2/3)*S-a7$	$(2/3)*S-a8$
$S-a15-a16$	$a15+a16-(1/3)*S$	$a1+a2-S/3$	$2*S/3-a2$	$2*S/3-a1$	$(2/3)*S-a13$	a13
a16	$(2/3)*S-a16$	$4*S/3-2*a1-a2$	$S/3$	$2*a1+a2-2*S/3$	$(2/3)*S-a14$	a14
a15	$(2/3)*S-a15$	a1	a2	$S-a1-a2$	$a13+a14-(1/3)*S$	$S-a13-a14$
$(2/3)*S+a8-a7-a9$	$(2/3)*S-a9$	$a7+2*a9+a10+a11+2*a12-a3+a4-(5/3)*S-a8$	$(2/3)*S-a10$	$(2/3)*S-a11$	$(2/3)*S-a12$	$(2/3)*S+a3-a4-a12$
$a7+a9-a8$	a9	$(7/3)*S+a8-a7-2*a9-a10-a11-2*a12+a3-a4$	a10	a11	a12	$a4+a12-a3$

• Details

It is an *algebraic magic square of order 7* composed of two equal sums magic rectangles of orders 2×7 and two equal sum magic rectangles of order 2×3 embedded with a magic square of order 3. For simplicity, this types of magic squares we call as **flat-type**. Thus we have an **algebraic flat-type** magic square of order 7. In this case, the magic sums are $S_{3 \times 3} := S$ and $S_{7 \times 7} := \frac{7S}{3}$. The width of magic rectangles is given as $m := \frac{2S}{3}$. In order to avoid decimal entries the magic sum of order 3 should be multiple of 3. Below are two examples.

Example 2.3. Let's consider following two examples based on the Result 2.3:

7	mgc							133	7	mgc							140		
		16	19	22	25	-8	28	31	133			16	19	22	25	-1	28	31	140
		22	19	16	13	46	10	7	133			24	21	18	15	41	12	9	140
		-50	88	4	25	28	-8	46	133			-47	87	3	27	30	-6	46	140
		55	-17	43	19	-5	-11	49	133			55	-15	47	20	-7	-9	49	140
		52	-14	10	13	34	76	-38	133			52	-12	10	13	37	75	-35	140
		7	4	136	1	-2	-5	-8	133			9	6	131	3	0	-3	-6	140
		31	34	-98	37	40	43	46	133			31	34	-91	37	40	43	46	140
		133	133	133	133	133	133	133	133			140	140	140	140	140	140	140	140

The magic sums are:

- First example: $S_{3 \times 3} := 57, S_{7 \times 7} := 133$ and $m := 38$.
- Second example: $S_{3 \times 3} := 60, S_{7 \times 7} := 140$ and $m := 40$.

2.2.3 Cornered

Result 2.4. Let's consider an algebraic magic square of order 7 with reduced entries:

$a_1 + a_2 - S/3$	$2*S/3 - a_2$	$2*S/3 - a_1$	$2*S/3 - a_3$	a_3	$2*S/3 - a_7$	a_7
$4*S/3 - 2*a_1 - a_2$	$S/3$	$2*a_1 + a_2 - 2*S/3$	$2*S/3 - a_4$	a_4	$2*S/3 - a_8$	a_8
a_1	a_2	$S - a_1 - a_2$	$a_3 + a_4 - (1/3)*S$	$S - a_3 - a_4$	$2*S/3 - a_9$	a_9
$(4/3)*S + a_3 - a_4 - a_1 - a_2 - a_5$	$2*S/3 - a_5$	$a_4 + a_1 + a_2 + 2*a_5 + 2*a_6 - (5/3)*S - a_3$	$2*S/3 - a_6$	$2*S/3 - a_6$	$2*S/3 - a_{10}$	a_{10}
$a_4 + a_1 + a_2 + a_5 - (2/3)*S - a_3$	a_5	$(7/3)*S + a_3 - a_4 - a_1 - a_2 - 2*a_5 - 2*a_6$	a_6	a_6	$a_7 + a_8 + a_9 + a_{10} - S$	$(5/3)*S - a_7 - a_8 - a_9 - a_{10}$
$(11/3)*S + a_7 - a_8 - 2*a_4 - 3*a_6 - a_1 - a_2 - 2*a_5 - a_{11}$	$2*S/3 - a_{11}$	$2*S/3 - a_{12}$	$2*S/3 - a_{13}$	$a_8 + 2*a_4 + 3*a_6 + a_1 + a_2 + 2*a_5 + 2*a_{11} + a_{12} + a_{13} + 2*a_{14} - (14/3)*S - a_7$	$2*S/3 - a_{14}$	$2*S/3 - a_{14}$
$a_8 + 2*a_4 + 3*a_6 + a_1 + a_2 + 2*a_5 + a_{11} - 3*S - a_7$	a_{11}	a_{12}	a_{13}	$(16/3)*S + a_7 - a_8 - 2*a_4 - 3*a_6 - a_1 - a_2 - 2*a_5 - 2*a_{11} - a_{12} - a_{13} - 2*a_{14}$	a_{14}	a_{14}

• **Details**

It is an **algebraic cornered**, where the magic squares of orders 3 and 5 are at the upper-left corner. In this case, the magic sums are $S_{3 \times 3} := S$, $S_{5 \times 5} := \frac{5S}{3}$ and $S_{7 \times 7} := \frac{7S}{3}$. The width of magic rectangles is given as $m := \frac{2S}{3}$. In order to avoid decimal entries the magic sum of order 3 should be multiple of 3. Below are two examples.

Example 2.4. Let's consider following two examples based on the Result 2.4:

7	mgc						119	7	mgc						147		
	6	21	24	18	16	6	28	119		2	29	32	26	16	14	28	147
	35	17	-1	15	19	3	31	119		51	21	-9	23	19	11	31	147
	10	13	28	18	16	0	34	119		10	13	40	14	28	8	34	147
	20	12	35	9	9	-3	37	119		36	20	15	17	17	5	37	147
	14	22	-1	25	25	79	-45	119		6	22	27	25	25	67	-25	147
	-36	-6	-9	-12	212	-15	-15	119		8	2	-1	-4	156	-7	-7	147
	70	40	43	46	-178	49	49	119		34	40	43	46	-114	49	49	147
	119	119	119	119	119	119	119	119		147	147	147	147	147	147	147	147

The magic sums are:

- **First example:** $S_{3 \times 3} := 51, S_{5 \times 5} := 85, S_{7 \times 7} := 119$ and $m := 34$.
- **Second example:** $S_{3 \times 3} := 63, S_{5 \times 5} := 105, S_{7 \times 7} := 147$ and $m := 42$.

2.3 Double-Digit Algebraic Magic Squares of Order 9

Below are three different ways of writing magic square of order 9, i.e., **cyclic, flat and cornered**.

2.3.1 Cyclic-Type

Result 2.5. Let's consider an **algebraic magic square of order 9 with reduced entries**:

a9	a10	a11	a12	a13	a14	$(7/5)*S-a9-a10-a11-a12-a13-a14$	$2*S/5-a15$	a15
$2*S/5-a9$	$2*S/5-a10$	$2*S/5-a11$	$2*S/5-a12$	$2*S/5-a13$	$2*S/5-a14$	$a9+a10+a11+a12+a13+a14-S$	$2*S/5-a16$	a16
$(7/5)*S-a30-a29-a28-a27-2*a26+a15-a16$	$a30+a29+a28+a27+2*a26-a15+a16-S$	a1	a2	$S-a1-a2-a3-a4$	a3	a4	$2*S/5-a17$	a17
a30	$2*S/5-a30$	$a8-a2+a7$	a5	$a1+a2+a3+a4-a5-a6-a7$	a6	$S-a1-a3-a4-a8$	$2*S/5-a18$	a18
a29	$2*S/5-a29$	$a2+a3+a4-a5-a7$	$S-a1-a2-a3-a4+a6-a8$	a7	$a7-a2-a3+a5+a8$	$a1+a2+a3-a6-a7$	$2*S/5-a19$	a19
a28	$2*S/5-a28$	$a7-a3+a5$	$a1-a6+a8$	$a2+a3-a7$	$S-a1-a5-a7-a8$	$a7-a2+a6$	$2*S/5-a20$	a20
a27	$2*S/5-a27$	$S-a1-a4-a7-a8$	$a3+a4-a5$	$a7-a2-a3+a5+a6$	$a1+a2-a6$	a8	$a15+a16+a17+a18+a19+a20-S$	$(7/5)*S-a15-a16-a17-a18-a19-a20$
a26	$2*S/5-a26$	$a25+a24+a23+a22+2*a21-a9+a10-S$	$2*S/5-a25$	$2*S/5-a24$	$2*S/5-a23$	$2*S/5-a22$	$2*S/5-a21$	$(2/5)*S+a9-a10-a21$
$a16+a26-a15$	$(2/5)*S+a15-a16-a26$	$(7/5)*S-a25-a24-a23-a22-2*a21+a9-a10$	a25	a24	a23	a22	a21	$a10+a21-a9$

• **Details**

It is an **algebraic cyclic-type** magic square of order 9 composed of four equal sums magic rectangles of orders 2×7 and embedded with a magic square of order 5. In this case, the magic sums are $S_{5 \times 5} := S$ and $S_{9 \times 9} := \frac{9S}{5}$. The width of magic rectangles is given as $m := \frac{2S}{5}$. In order to avoid decimal entries the magic sum of order 5 should be multiple of 5. Below are two examples.

Example 2.5. Let's consider following two examples based on the Result 2.5:

9	mgc	9x9 https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT								81	
		19	20	21	22	23	24	-66	-7	25	81
		-1	-2	-3	-4	-5	-6	84	-8	26	81
		-164	182	11	12	-5	13	14	-9	27	81
		40	-22	23	15	2	16	-11	-10	28	81
		39	-21	7	-7	17	25	3	-11	29	81
		38	-20	19	13	8	-16	21	-12	30	81
		37	-19	-15	12	23	7	18	120	-102	81
		36	-18	152	-17	-16	-15	-14	-13	-14	81
		37	-19	-134	35	34	33	32	31	32	81
		81	81	81	81	81	81	81	81	81	81

9	mgc	9x9 https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT								90	
		19	20	21	22	23	24	-59	-5	25	90
		1	0	-1	-2	-3	-4	79	-6	26	90
		-157	177	11	12	0	13	14	-7	27	90
		40	-20	23	15	2	16	-6	-8	28	90
		39	-19	7	-2	17	25	3	-9	29	90
		38	-18	19	13	8	-11	21	-10	30	90
		37	-17	-10	12	23	7	18	115	-95	90
		36	-16	147	-15	-14	-13	-12	-11	-12	90
		37	-17	-127	35	34	33	32	31	32	90
		90	90	90	90	90	90	90	90	90	90

The magic sums are:

- **First example:** $S_{5 \times 5} := 45, S_{9 \times 9} := 81$ and $m := 18$.
- **Second example:** $S_{5 \times 5} := 50, S_{9 \times 9} := 90$ and $m := 20$.

2.3.2 Flat-Type

Result 2.6. Let's consider an *algebraic magic square of order 9 with reduced entries*:

a9	a10	a11	a12	a13	a14	$(9/5)*S - a9 - a10 - a11 - a12 - a13 - a14 - a15 - a16$	a15	a16
$2*S/5 - a9$	$2*S/5 - a10$	$2*S/5 - a11$	$2*S/5 - a12$	$2*S/5 - a13$	$2*S/5 - a14$	$a9 + a10 + a11 + a12 + a13 + a14 + a15 + a16 - (7/5)*S$	$2*S/5 - a15$	$2*S/5 - a16$
$S - a27 - a28 - a29 - a30$	$a27 + a28 + a29 + a30 - (3/5)*S$	a1	a2	$S - a1 - a2 - a3 - a4$	a3	a4	$2*S/5 - a23$	a23
a27	$2*S/5 - a27$	$a8 - a2 + a7$	a5	$a1 + a2 + a3 + a4 - a5 - a6 - a7$	a6	$S - a1 - a3 - a4 - a8$	$2*S/5 - a24$	a24
a28	$2*S/5 - a28$	$a2 + a3 + a4 - a5 - a7$	$S - a1 - a2 - a3 - a4 + a6 - a8$	a7	$a7 - a2 - a3 + a5 + a8$	$a1 + a2 + a3 - a6 - a7$	$2*S/5 - a25$	a25
a29	$2*S/5 - a29$	$a7 - a3 + a5$	$a1 - a6 + a8$	$a2 + a3 - a7$	$S - a1 - a5 - a7 - a8$	$a7 - a2 + a6$	$2*S/5 - a26$	a26
a30	$2*S/5 - a30$	$S - a1 - a4 - a7 - a8$	$a3 + a4 - a5$	$a7 - a2 - a3 + a5 + a6$	$a1 + a2 - a6$	a8	$a23 + a24 + a25 + a26 - (3/5)*S$	$S - a23 - a24 - a25 - a26$
$(2/5)*S + a16 - a15 - a17$	$2*S/5 - a17$	$a15 + 2*a17 + a18 + a19 + a20 + a21 + 2*a22 - a9 + a10 - (7/5)*S - a16$	$2*S/5 - a18$	$2*S/5 - a19$	$2*S/5 - a20$	$2*S/5 - a21$	$2*S/5 - a22$	$(2/5)*S + a9 - a10 - a22$
$a15 + a17 - a16$	a17	$(9/5)*S + a16 - a15 - 2*a17 - a18 - a19 - a20 - a21 - 2*a22 + a9 - a10$	a18	a19	a20	a21	a22	$a10 + a22 - a9$

• Details

It is an *algebraic flat-type* magic square of order 9 composed of two equal sums magic rectangles of orders 2×9 and two equal sum magic rectangles of order 2×5 embedded with a magic square of order 5. In this case, the magic sums are $S_{5 \times 5} := S$ and $S_{9 \times 9} := \frac{9S}{5}$. The width of magic rectangles is given as $m := \frac{2S}{5}$. In order to avoid decimal entries the magic sum of order 5 should be multiple of 5. Below are two examples.

Example 2.6. Let's consider following two examples based on the Result 2.6:

9	mgc	9x9 https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT								153	9	mgc	9x9 https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT								189		
		35	38	41	44	47	50	-211	53	56	153			35	38	41	44	47	50	-175	53	56	189
		-1	-4	-7	-10	-13	-16	245	-19	-22	153			7	4	1	-2	-5	-8	217	-11	-14	189
		-289	323	11	14	23	17	20	-43	77	153			-269	311	11	14	43	17	20	-35	77	189
		89	-55	47	23	-16	26	5	-46	80	153			89	-47	47	23	-16	26	25	-38	80	189
		92	-58	-1	17	29	53	-13	-49	83	153			92	-50	-1	37	29	53	-13	-41	83	189
		95	-61	35	17	2	-10	41	-52	86	153			95	-53	35	17	2	10	41	-44	86	189
		98	-64	-7	14	47	-1	32	275	-241	153			98	-56	13	14	47	-1	32	263	-221	189
		-22	-25	413	-28	-31	-34	-37	-40	-43	153			-14	-17	385	-20	-23	-26	-29	-32	-35	189
		56	59	-379	62	65	68	71	74	77	153			56	59	-343	62	65	68	71	74	77	189
		153	153	153	153	153	153	153	153	153	153			189	189	189	189	189	189	189	189	189	189

The magic sums are:

- First example: $S_{5 \times 5} := 85, S_{9 \times 9} := 153$ and $m := 34$.
- Second example: $S_{5 \times 5} := 105, S_{9 \times 9} := 189$ and $m := 42$.

2.3.3 Cornered

Result 2.7. Let's consider an algebraic magic square of order 9 with reduced entries:

$a_1+a_2-S/3$	$2*S/3-a_2$	$2*S/3-a_1$	$2*S/3-a_3$	a_3	$2*S/3-a_7$	a_7	$2*S/3-a_{15}$	a_{15}
$4*S/3-2*a_1-a_2$	$S/3$	$2*a_1+a_2-2*S/3$	$2*S/3-a_4$	a_4	$2*S/3-a_8$	a_8	$2*S/3-a_{16}$	a_{16}
a_1	a_2	$S-a_1-a_2$	$a_3+a_4-(1/3)*S$	$S-a_3-a_4$	$2*S/3-a_9$	a_9	$2*S/3-a_{17}$	a_{17}
$(4/3)*S+a_3-a_4-a_1-a_2-a_5$	$2*S/3-a_5$	$a_4+a_1+a_2+2*a_5+2*a_6-(5/3)*S-a_3$	$2*S/3-a_6$	$2*S/3-a_6$	$2*S/3-a_{10}$	a_{10}	$2*S/3-a_{18}$	a_{18}
$a_4+a_1+a_2+a_5-(2/3)*S-a_3$	a_5	$(7/3)*S+a_3-a_4-a_1-a_2-2*a_5-2*a_6$	a_6	a_6	$a_7+a_8+a_9+a_{10}-S$	$(5/3)*S-a_7-a_8-a_9-a_{10}$	$2*S/3-a_{19}$	a_{19}
$(11/3)*S+a_7-a_8-2*a_4-3*a_6-a_1-a_2-2*a_5-a_{11}$	$2*S/3-a_{11}$	$2*S/3-a_{12}$	$2*S/3-a_{13}$	$a_8+2*a_4+3*a_6+a_1+a_2+2*a_5+2*a_{11}+a_{12}+a_{13}+2*a_{14}-(14/3)*S-a_7$	$2*S/3-a_{14}$	$2*S/3-a_{14}$	$2*S/3-a_{20}$	a_{20}
$a_8+2*a_4+3*a_6+a_1+a_2+2*a_5+a_{11}-3*S-a_7$	a_{11}	a_{12}	a_{13}	$(16/3)*S+a_7-a_8-2*a_4-3*a_6-a_1-a_2-2*a_5-2*a_{11}-a_{12}-a_{13}-2*a_{14}$	a_{14}	a_{14}	$a_{15}+a_{16}+a_{17}+a_{18}+a_{19}+a_2-0-(5/3)*S$	$(7/3)*S-a_{15}-a_{16}-a_{17}-a_{18}-a_{19}-a_{20}$
$(1/3)*S+a_{15}-a_{16}+a_9-a_{10}+a_6-a_{13}+a_{12}-a_{21}$	$2*S/3-a_{21}$	$2*S/3-a_{22}$	$2*S/3-a_{23}$	$2*S/3-a_{24}$	$2*S/3-a_{25}$	$a_{16}-a_9+a_{10}-a_6+a_{13}-a_{12}+2*a_{21}+a_{22}+a_{23}+a_{24}+a_{25}+2*a_{26}-2*S-a_{15}$	$2*S/3-a_{26}$	$2*S/3-a_{26}$
$(1/3)*S-a_{15}+a_{16}-a_9+a_{10}-a_6+a_{13}-a_{12}+a_{21}$	a_{21}	a_{22}	a_{23}	a_{24}	a_{25}	$(8/3)*S+a_{15}-a_{16}+a_9-a_{10}+a_6-a_{13}+a_{12}-2*a_{21}-a_{22}-a_{23}-a_{24}-a_{25}-2*a_{26}$	a_{26}	a_{26}

• **Details**

It is an **algebraic cornered**, where the magic squares of orders 3, 5 and 7 are at the upper-left corner. In this case, the magic sums are $S_{3 \times 3} := S$, $S_{5 \times 5} := \frac{5S}{3}$, $S_{7 \times 7} := \frac{7S}{3}$ and $S_{9 \times 9} := 3S$. The width of magic rectangles is given as $m := \frac{2S}{3}$. In order to avoid decimal entries the magic sum of order 3 should be multiple of 3. Below are two examples.

Example 2.7. Let's consider following two examples based on the Result 2.7:

9	mgc	9x9 https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT								117	
		10	14	15	13	13	9	17	1	25	117
		18	13	8	12	14	8	18	0	26	117
		11	12	16	14	12	7	19	-1	27	117
		13	11	21	10	10	6	20	-2	28	117
		13	15	5	16	16	35	-9	-3	29	117
		-8	5	4	3	83	2	2	-4	30	117
		34	21	22	23	-57	24	24	100	-74	117
		-5	-5	-6	-7	-8	-9	177	-10	-10	117
		31	31	32	33	34	35	-151	36	36	117
		117	117	117	117	117	117	117	117	117	117

9	mgc	9x9 https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT								126	
		9	16	17	15	13	11	17	3	25	126
		22	14	6	14	14	10	18	2	26	126
		11	12	19	13	15	9	19	1	27	126
		17	13	16	12	12	8	20	0	28	126
		11	15	12	16	16	32	-4	-1	29	126
		3	7	6	5	69	4	4	-2	30	126
		25	21	22	23	-41	24	24	95	-67	126
		-4	-3	-4	-5	-6	-7	171	-8	-8	126
		32	31	32	33	34	35	-143	36	36	126
		126	126	126	126	126	126	126	126	126	126

The magic sums are:

- **First example:** $S_{3 \times 3} := 39$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 65$, $S_{7 \times 7} := 91$, $S_{9 \times 9} := 117$ and $m := 26$.
- **Second example:** $S_{3 \times 3} := 42$, $S_{5 \times 5} := 70$, $S_{7 \times 7} := 98$, $S_{9 \times 9} := 126$ and $m := 28$.

2.4 Double-Digit Algebraic Magic Squares of Order 11

Below are three different ways of writing magic square of order 11, i.e., **cyclic**, **flat** and **cornered**.

2.4.1 Cyclic-Type

Result 2.8. Let's consider an **algebraic magic square of order 11 with reduced entries**:

a17	a18	a19	a20	a21	a22	a23	a24	$3^*S - a17 - a18 - a19 - a20 - a21 - a22 - a23 - a24$	$(2/3)^*S - a25$	a25
$(2/3)^*S - a17$	$(2/3)^*S - a18$	$(2/3)^*S - a19$	$(2/3)^*S - a20$	$(2/3)^*S - a21$	$(2/3)^*S - a22$	$(2/3)^*S - a23$	$(2/3)^*S - a24$	$a17 + a18 + a19 + a20 + a21 + a22 + a23 + a24 - (7/3)^*S$	$(2/3)^*S - a26$	a26
$3^*S - a47 - a46 - a45 - a44 - a43 - a42 - 2^*a41 + a25 - a26$	$a47 + a46 + a45 + a44 + a43 + a42 + 2^*a41 - a25 + a26 - (7/3)^*S$	a3	a4	a5	a6	$(5/3)^*S - a3 - a4 - a5 - a6$	$(2/3)^*S - a7$	a7	$(2/3)^*S - a27$	a27
a47	$(2/3)^*S - a47$	$(2/3)^*S - a3$	$(2/3)^*S - a4$	$(2/3)^*S - a5$	$(2/3)^*S - a6$	$a3 + a4 + a5 + a6 - S$	$(2/3)^*S - a8$	a8	$(2/3)^*S - a28$	a28
a46	$(2/3)^*S - a46$	$(5/3)^*S + a7 - a8 - 2^*a14 - a15 - a16$	$a8 + 2^*a14 + a15 + a16 - S - a7$	$a1 + a2 - S/3$	$2^*S/3 - a2$	$2^*S/3 - a1$	$(2/3)^*S - a9$	a9	$(2/3)^*S - a29$	a29
a45	$(2/3)^*S - a45$	a16	$(2/3)^*S - a16$	$4^*S/3 - 2^*a1 - a2$	$S/3$	$2^*a1 + a2 - 2^*S/3$	$(2/3)^*S - a10$	a10	$(2/3)^*S - a30$	a30
a44	$(2/3)^*S - a44$	a15	$(2/3)^*S - a15$	a1	a2	$S - a1 - a2$	$a7 + a8 + a9 + a10 - S$	$(5/3)^*S - a7 - a8 - a9 - a10$	$(2/3)^*S - a31$	a31
a43	$(2/3)^*S - a43$	a14	$(2/3)^*S - a14$	$a4 + 2^*a11 + a12 + a13 - S - a3$	$(2/3)^*S - a13$	$(2/3)^*S - a12$	$(2/3)^*S - a11$	$(2/3)^*S + a3 - a4 - a11$	$(2/3)^*S - a32$	a32
a42	$(2/3)^*S - a42$	$a8 + a14 - a7$	$(2/3)^*S + a7 - a8 - a14$	$(5/3)^*S + a3 - a4 - 2^*a11 - a12 - a13$	a13	a12	a11	$a4 + a11 - a3$	$a25 + a26 + a27 + a28 + a29 + a30 + a31 + a32 - (7/3)^*S$	$3^*S - a25 - a26 - a27 - a28 - a29 - a30 - a31 - a32$
a41	$(2/3)^*S - a41$	$a39 + a38 + a37 + a36 + a35 + a34 + 2^*a33 - a17 + a18 - (7/3)^*S$	$(2/3)^*S - a39$	$(2/3)^*S - a38$	$(2/3)^*S - a37$	$(2/3)^*S - a36$	$(2/3)^*S - a35$	$(2/3)^*S - a34$	$(2/3)^*S - a33$	$(2/3)^*S + a17 - a18 - a33$
$a26 + a41 - a25$	$(2/3)^*S + a25 - a26 - a41$	$3^*S - a39 - a38 - a37 - a36 - a35 - a34 - 2^*a33 + a17 - a18$	a39	a38	a37	a36	a35	a34	a33	$a18 + a33 - a17$

• Details

It is an **algebraic cyclic-type** magic square of order 11 composed of four equal sums magic rectangles of orders 2×9 . It is again composed of four equal sums magic rectangles of order 2×5 having a magic square of order 3 in the middle. In this case, the magic sums are $S_{3 \times 3} := S$, $S_{7 \times 7} := \frac{7S}{3}$ and $S_{11 \times 11} := \frac{11S}{3}$. The width of magic rectangles is given as $m := \frac{2S}{3}$. In order to avoid decimal entries the magic sum of order 3 should be multiple of 3. Below are two examples.

Example 2.8. Let's consider following two examples based on the Result 2.8:

11	mgc	11x11 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										121	11	mgc	11x11 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										143
18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	-73	-4	26	121	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	-55	0	26	143		
4	3	2	1	0	-1	-2	-3	95	-5	27	121	8	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	81	-1	27	143		
-259	281	4	5	6	7	33	14	8	-6	28	121	-241	267	4	5	6	7	43	18	8	-2	28	143		
48	-26	18	17	16	15	-11	13	9	-7	29	121	48	-22	22	21	20	19	-17	17	9	-3	29	143		
47	-25	-9	31	-6	19	20	12	10	-8	30	121	47	-21	1	25	-8	23	24	16	10	-4	30	143		
46	-24	17	5	37	11	-15	11	11	-9	31	121	46	-20	17	9	45	13	-19	15	11	-5	31	143		
45	-23	16	6	2	3	28	5	17	-10	32	121	45	-19	16	10	2	3	34	-1	27	-6	32	143		
44	-22	15	7	19	8	9	10	9	-11	33	121	44	-18	15	11	13	12	13	14	13	-7	33	143		
43	-21	16	6	3	14	13	12	13	159	-137	121	43	-17	16	10	13	14	13	12	13	145	-119	143		
42	-20	217	-18	-17	-16	-15	-14	-13	-12	-13	121	42	-16	203	-14	-13	-12	-11	-10	-9	-8	-9	143		
43	-21	-195	40	39	38	37	36	35	34	35	121	43	-17	-177	40	39	38	37	36	35	34	35	143		
121	121	121	121	121	121	121	121	121	121	121	121	143	143	143	143	143	143	143	143	143	143	143			

The magic sums are:

- **First example:** $S_{3 \times 3} := 33, S_{7 \times 7} := 77, S_{11 \times 11} := 121$ and $m := 22$.
- **Second example:** $S_{3 \times 3} := 39, S_{7 \times 7} := 91, S_{11 \times 11} := 143$ and $m := 26$.

2.4.2 Flat-Type

Result 2.9. Let's consider an algebraic magic square of order 11 with reduced entries:

a17	a18	a19	a20	a21	a22	a23	a24	$(11/3)*S-a17-a18-a19-a20-a21-a22-a23-a24-a25-a26$	a25	a26
$(2/3)*S-a17$	$(2/3)*S-a18$	$(2/3)*S-a19$	$(2/3)*S-a20$	$(2/3)*S-a21$	$(2/3)*S-a22$	$(2/3)*S-a23$	$(2/3)*S-a24$	$a17+a18+a19+a20+a21+a22+a23+a24+a25+a26-3*S$	$(2/3)*S-a25$	$(2/3)*S-a26$
$(7/3)*S-a46-a45-a44-a43-a42-a41$	$a46+a45+a44+a43+a42+a41-(5/3)*S$	a3	a4	a5	a6	$(7/3)*S-a3-a4-a5-a6-a7-a8$	a7	a8	$(2/3)*S-a27$	a27
a46	$(2/3)*S-a46$	$(2/3)*S-a3$	$(2/3)*S-a4$	$(2/3)*S-a5$	$(2/3)*S-a6$	$a3+a4+a5+a6+a7+a8-(5/3)*S$	$(2/3)*S-a7$	$(2/3)*S-a8$	$(2/3)*S-a28$	a28
a45	$(2/3)*S-a45$	$S-a15-a16$	$a15+a16-(1/3)*S$	$a1+a2-S/3$	$2*S/3-a2$	$2*S/3-a1$	$(2/3)*S-a13$	a13	$(2/3)*S-a29$	a29
a44	$(2/3)*S-a44$	a16	$(2/3)*S-a16$	$4*S/3-2*a1-a2$	S/3	$2*a1+a2-2*S/3$	$(2/3)*S-a14$	a14	$(2/3)*S-a30$	a30
a43	$(2/3)*S-a43$	a15	$(2/3)*S-a15$	a1	a2	$S-a1-a2$	$a13+a14-(1/3)*S$	$S-a13-a14$	$(2/3)*S-a31$	a31
a42	$(2/3)*S-a42$	$(2/3)*S+a8-a7-a9$	$(2/3)*S-a9$	$a7+2*a9+a10+a11+2*a12-a3+a4-(5/3)*S-a8$	$(2/3)*S-a10$	$(2/3)*S-a11$	$(2/3)*S-a12$	$(2/3)*S+a3-a4-a12$	$(2/3)*S-a32$	a32
a41	$(2/3)*S-a41$	$a7+a9-a8$	a9	$(7/3)*S+a8-a7-2*a9-a10-a11-2*a12+a3-a4$	a10	a11	a12	$a4+a12-a3$	$a27+a28+a29+a30+a31+a32-2*(5/3)*S$	$(7/3)*S-a27-a28-a29-a30-a31-a32$
$(2/3)*S+a26-a25-a40$	$(2/3)*S-a40$	$a34+2*a33+a35+a36-a17+a37+a18+a38-a26+a25+2*a40+a39-3*S$	$(2/3)*S-a39$	$(2/3)*S-a38$	$(2/3)*S-a37$	$(2/3)*S-a36$	$(2/3)*S-a35$	$(2/3)*S-a34$	$(2/3)*S-a33$	$(2/3)*S+a17-a18-a33$
$a25+a40-a26$	a40	$(11/3)*S-a34-2*a33-a35-a36+a17-a37-a18-a38+a26-a25-2*a40-a39$	a39	a38	a37	a36	a35	a34	a33	$a18+a33-a17$

• **Details**

It is an **algebraic flat-type** magic square of order 11 composed of two equal sums magic rectangles of orders 2×11 and two equal sums magic rectangles of order 2×7 embedded again with a **flat-type** magic square of order 7. In this case the magic sums are $S_{3 \times 3} := S$, $S_{7 \times 7} := \frac{7S}{3}$ and $S_{11 \times 11} := \frac{11S}{3}$, where S is the magic sum of order 3. In this case, $m := \frac{2S}{3}$ is the width of magic rectangles. To avoid decimal entries the magic sums of order 3 should be multiple of 3. See below two examples:

Example 2.9. Let's consider following two examples based on the Result 2.9:

11	mgc	11x11 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										176											
17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	-39	25	26	176	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	-28	25	26	187
15	14	13	12	11	10	9	8	71	7	6	176	17	16	15	14	13	12	11	10	62	9	8	187
-149	181	3	4	5	6	79	7	8	5	27	176	-142	176	3	4	5	6	86	7	8	7	27	187
46	-14	29	28	27	26	-47	25	24	4	28	176	46	-12	31	30	29	28	-52	27	26	6	28	187
45	-13	17	15	-13	30	31	19	13	3	29	176	45	-11	20	14	-14	32	33	21	13	5	29	187
44	-12	16	16	60	16	-28	18	14	2	30	176	44	-10	16	18	64	17	-30	20	14	4	30	187
43	-11	15	17	1	2	45	11	21	1	31	176	43	-9	15	19	1	2	48	10	24	3	31	187
42	-10	24	23	-17	22	21	20	19	0	32	176	42	-8	26	25	-22	24	23	22	21	2	32	187
41	-9	8	9	49	10	11	12	13	97	-65	176	41	-7	8	9	56	10	11	12	13	92	-58	187
-7	-8	221	-7	-6	-5	-4	-3	-2	-1	-2	176	-5	-6	212	-5	-4	-3	-2	-1	0	1	0	187
39	40	-189	39	38	37	36	35	34	33	34	176	39	40	-178	39	38	37	36	35	34	33	34	187
176	176	176	176	176	176	176	176	176	176	176	176	187	187	187	187	187	187	187	187	187	187	187	

The magic sums are:

- **First example:** $S_{3 \times 3} := 48, S_{7 \times 7} := 112, S_{11 \times 11} := 176$ and $m := 32$.
- **Second example:** $S_{3 \times 3} := 51, S_{7 \times 7} := 119, S_{11 \times 11} := 187$ and $m := 34$.

2.4.3 Cornered

Result 2.10. Let's consider an **algebraic magic square** of order 11 with **reduced entries**:

$a1+a2-S/3$	$2^*S/3-a2$	$2^*S/3-a1$	$2^*S/3-a3$	$a3$	$2^*S/3-a7$	$a7$	$2^*S/3-a15$	$a15$	$2^*S/3-a27$	$a27$
$4^*S/3-2^*a1-a2$	$S/3$	$2^*a1+a2-2^*S/3$	$2^*S/3-a4$	$a4$	$2^*S/3-a8$	$a8$	$2^*S/3-a16$	$a16$	$2^*S/3-a28$	$a28$
$a1$	$a2$	$S-a1-a2$	$a3+a4-(1/3)^*S$	$S-a3-a4$	$2^*S/3-a9$	$a9$	$2^*S/3-a17$	$a17$	$2^*S/3-a29$	$a29$
$(4/3)^*S+a3-a4-a1-a2-a5$	$2^*S/3-a5$	$a4+a1+a2+2^*a5+2^*a6-(5/3)^*S-a3$	$2^*S/3-a6$	$2^*S/3-a6$	$2^*S/3-a10$	$a10$	$2^*S/3-a18$	$a18$	$2^*S/3-a30$	$a30$
$a4+a1+a2+a5-(2/3)^*S-a3$	$a5$	$(7/3)^*S+a3-a4-a1-a2-2^*a5-2^*a6$	$a6$	$a6$	$a7+a8+a9+a10-S$	$(5/3)^*S-a7-a8-a9-a10$	$2^*S/3-a19$	$a19$	$2^*S/3-a31$	$a31$
$(11/3)^*S+a7-a8-2^*a4-3^*a6-a1-a2-2^*a5-a11$	$2^*S/3-a11$	$2^*S/3-a12$	$2^*S/3-a13$	$a8+2^*a4+3^*a6+a1+a2+2^*a5+2^*a11+a12+a13+2^*a14-(14/3)^*S-a7$	$2^*S/3-a14$	$2^*S/3-a14$	$2^*S/3-a20$	$a20$	$2^*S/3-a32$	$a32$
$a8+2^*a4+3^*a6+a1+a2+2^*a5+a11-3^*S-a7$	$a11$	$a12$	$a13$	$(16/3)^*S+a7-a8-2^*a4-3^*a6-a1-a2-2^*a5-2^*a11-a12-a13-2^*a14$	$a14$	$a14$	$a15+a16+a17+a18+a19+a20-(5/3)^*S$	$(7/3)^*S-a15-a16-a17-a18-a19-a20$	$2^*S/3-a33$	$a33$
$S+a15-a16+a9-a10+a6-a13+a12-a21$	$2^*S/3-a21$	$2^*S/3-a22$	$2^*S/3-a23$	$2^*S/3-a24$	$2^*S/3-a25$	$a16-a9+a10-a6+a13-a12+2^*a21+a22+a23+a24+a25+2^*a26-(8/3)^*S-a15$	$2^*S/3-a26$	$2^*S/3-a26$	$2^*S/3-a34$	$a34$
$a16-a9+a10-a6+a13-a12+a21-(1/3)^*S-a15$	$a21$	$a22$	$a23$	$a24$	$a25$	$(10/3)^*S+a15-a16+a9-a10+a6-a13+a12-2^*a21-a22-a23-a24-a25-2^*a26$	$a26$	$a26$	$a27+a28+a29+a30+a31+a32+a33+a34-(7/3)^*S$	$3^*S-a27-a28-a29-a30-a31-a32-a33-a34$
$(22/3)^*S+a22-3^*a14-a35-2^*a11-a10+a17-a13-a9-a18-a12-a1-a2-a23-2^*a8-a28-3^*a6+a27-2^*a5-2^*a4$	$2^*S/3-a35$	$2^*S/3-a36$	$2^*S/3-a37$	$2^*S/3-a38$	$2^*S/3-a39$	$2^*S/3-a40$	$2^*S/3-a41$	$3^*a14+a41+2^*a42+2^*a35+a36+2^*a11+a10-a17+a13+a9+a37+a18+a12+a1+a2+a38+a23+2^*a8+a40+a28+3^*a6-a27+2^*a5+2^*a4-(29/3)^*S+a39-a22$	$2^*S/3-a42$	$2^*S/3-a42$
$3^*a14+a35+2^*a11+a10-a17+a13+a9+a18+a12+a1+a2+a23+2^*a8+a28+3^*a6-a27+2^*a5+2^*a4-(20/3)^*S-a22$	$a35$	$a36$	$a37$	$a38$	$a39$	$a40$	$a41$	$a22-3^*a14-a41-2^*a42-2^*a35-a36-2^*a11-a10+a17-a13-a9-a37-a18-a12-a1-a2-a38-a23-2^*a8-a40-a28-3^*a6+a27-2^*a5-2^*a4+(31/3)^*S-a39$	$a42$	$a42$

• **Details**

It is an **algebraic cornered**, where the magic squares of orders 11, where the magic squares of order 3, 5, 7 and 9 are at the upper-left corner. In this case, the magic sums are $S_{3 \times 3} := S$, $S_{5 \times 5} := \frac{5S}{3}$, $S_{7 \times 7} := \frac{7S}{3}$, $S_{9 \times 9} := 3S$ and $S_{11 \times 11} := 11S/3$. The width of magic rectangles is given as $m := \frac{2S}{3}$. In order to avoid decimal entries the magic sum of order 3 should be multiple of 3. Below are two examples.

Example 2.10. Let's consider following two examples based on the Result 2.10:

11	mgc	11x11 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										198	11	mgc	11x11 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										209
3	25	26	24	12	20	16	12	24	0	36	198	2	27	28	26	12	22	16	14	24	2	36	209		
41	18	-5	23	13	19	17	11	25	-1	37	198	45	19	-7	25	13	21	17	13	25	1	37	209		
10	11	33	7	29	18	18	10	26	-2	38	198	10	11	36	6	32	20	18	12	26	0	38	209		
36	22	-10	21	21	17	19	9	27	-3	39	198	40	24	-15	23	23	19	19	11	27	-1	39	209		
0	14	46	15	15	16	20	8	28	-4	40	198	-2	14	53	15	15	13	25	10	28	-2	40	209		
57	16	15	14	-2	13	13	7	29	-5	41	198	68	18	17	16	-16	15	15	9	29	-3	41	209		
-21	20	21	22	38	23	23	69	-33	-6	42	198	-30	20	21	22	54	23	23	64	-26	-4	42	209		
36	6	5	4	3	2	104	1	1	-7	43	198	39	8	7	6	5	4	96	3	3	-5	43	209		
0	30	31	32	33	34	-68	35	35	190	-154	198	-1	30	31	32	33	34	-58	35	35	183	-145	209		
6	-8	-9	-10	-11	-12	-13	-14	299	-15	-15	198	28	-6	-7	-8	-9	-10	-11	-12	270	-13	-13	209		
30	44	45	46	47	48	49	50	-263	51	51	198	10	44	45	46	47	48	49	50	-232	51	51	209		
198	198	198	198	198	198	198	198	198	198	198	198	209	209	209	209	209	209	209	209	209	209	209	209	209	

The magic sums are:

- **First example:** $S_{3 \times 3} := 54, S_{5 \times 5} := 90, S_{7 \times 7} := 126, S_{9 \times 9} := 162, S_{11 \times 11} := 198$ and $m := 36$.
- **Second example:** $S_{3 \times 3} := 57, S_{5 \times 5} := 95, S_{7 \times 7} := 133, S_{9 \times 9} := 171, S_{11 \times 11} := 209$ and $m := 38$.

2.5 Double-Digit Algebraic Magic Squares of Order 13

Below are three different ways of writing magic square of order 13, i.e., **cyclic**, **flat** and **cornered**.

2.5.1 Cyclic-Type

Result 2.11. Let's consider an *algebraic magic square of order 13 with reduced entries*:

a31	a32	a33	a34	a35	a36	a37	a38	a39	a40	$(11/5)*S-a31-a32-a34-a35-a36-a37-a38-a39-a40-a33$	$2*S/5-a41$	a41
$2*S/5-a31$	$2*S/5-a32$	$2*S/5-a33$	$2*S/5-a34$	$2*S/5-a35$	$2*S/5-a36$	$2*S/5-a37$	$2*S/5-a38$	$2*S/5-a39$	$2*S/5-a40$	$a31+a32+a34+a35+a36+a37+a38+a39+a40+a33-(9/5)*S$	$2*S/5-a42$	a42
$(11/5)*S+a41-a42-2*a60-a62-a63-a64-a65-a66-a67-a68-a61$	$a42+2*a60-a41+a62+a63+a64+a65+a66+a67+a68+a61-(9/5)*S$	a9	a10	a11	a12	a13	a14	$(7/5)*S-a9-a10-a11-a12-a13-a14$	$2*S/5-a15$	a15	$2*S/5-a43$	a43
a68	$2*S/5-a68$	$2*S/5-a9$	$2*S/5-a10$	$2*S/5-a11$	$2*S/5-a12$	$2*S/5-a13$	$2*S/5-a14$	$a9+a10+a11+a12+a13+a14-S$	$2*S/5-a16$	a16	$2*S/5-a44$	a44
a67	$2*S/5-a67$	$(7/5)*S-a30-a29-a28-a27-2*a26+a15-a16$	$a30+a29+a28+a27+2*a26-a15+a16-S$	a1	a2	$S-a1-a2-a3-a4$	a3	a4	$2*S/5-a17$	a17	$2*S/5-a45$	a45
a66	$2*S/5-a66$	a30	$2*S/5-a30$	$a8-a2+a7$	a5	$a1+a2+a3+a4+a5-a6-a7$	a6	$S-a1-a3-a4-a8$	$2*S/5-a18$	a18	$2*S/5-a46$	a46
a65	$2*S/5-a65$	a29	$2*S/5-a29$	$a2+a3+a4-a5-a7$	$S-a1-a2-a3-a4+a6-a8$	a7	$a7-a2-a3+a5+a8$	$a1+a2+a3-a6-a7$	$2*S/5-a19$	a19	$2*S/5-a47$	a47
a64	$2*S/5-a64$	a28	$2*S/5-a28$	$a7-a3+a5$	$a1-a6+a8$	$a2+a3-a7$	$S-a1-a5-a7-a8$	$a7-a2+a6$	$2*S/5-a20$	a20	$2*S/5-a48$	a48
a63	$2*S/5-a63$	a27	$2*S/5-a27$	$S-a1-a4-a7-a8$	$a3+a4-a5$	$a7-a2-a3+a5+a6$	$a1+a2-a6$	a8	$a15+a16+a17+a18+a19+a20-S$	$(7/5)*S-a15-a16-a17-a18-a19-a20$	$2*S/5-a49$	a49
a62	$2*S/5-a62$	a26	$2*S/5-a26$	$a25+a24+a23+a22+2*a21-a9+a10-S$	$2*S/5-a25$	$2*S/5-a24$	$2*S/5-a23$	$2*S/5-a22$	$2*S/5-a21$	$(2/5)*S+a9-a10-a21$	$2*S/5-a50$	a50
a61	$2*S/5-a61$	$a16+a26-a15$	$(2/5)*S+a15-a16-a26$	$(7/5)*S-a25-a24-a23-a22-2*a21+a9-a10$	a25	a24	a23	a22	a21	$a10+a21-a9$	$a42+a41+a50+a49+a48+a47+a46+a45+a44+a43-(9/5)*S$	$(11/5)*S-a42-a41-a50-a49-a48-a47-a46-a45-a44-a43$
a60	$2*S/5-a60$	$a32+2*a51-a31+a52+a53+a54+a55+a56+a57+a58+a59-(9/5)*S$	$2*S/5-a59$	$2*S/5-a58$	$2*S/5-a57$	$2*S/5-a56$	$2*S/5-a55$	$2*S/5-a54$	$2*S/5-a53$	$2*S/5-a52$	$2*S/5-a51$	$(2/5)*S+a31-a32-a51$
$a42+a60-a41$	$(2/5)*S+a41-a42-a60$	$(11/5)*S+a31-a32-2*a51-a52-a53-a54-a55-a56-a57-a58-a59$	a59	a58	a57	a56	a55	a54	a53	a52	a51	$a32+a51-a31$

• Details

It is an *algebraic cyclic-type* magic square of order 13 composed of four equal sums magic rectangles of orders 2×11 . It is again composed of four equal sums magic rectangles of order 2×7 having a magic square of order 3 in the middle. In this case, the magic sums are $S_{5 \times 5} := S, S_{9 \times 9} := \frac{9S}{5}$ and $S_{13 \times 13} := \frac{13S}{5}$. The width of magic rectangles is given as $m := \frac{2S}{5}$. In order to avoid decimal entries the magic sum of order 5 should be multiple of 5. Below are two examples.

Example 2.11. Let's consider following two examples based on the Result 2.11:

13	mgc	13x13 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT											169	
	32	33	34	35	36	37	38	39	40	41	-222	-16	42	169
	-6	-7	-8	-9	-10	-11	-12	-13	-14	-15	248	-17	43	169
	-504	530	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	10	16	-18	44	169
	69	-43	16	15	14	13	12	11	10	9	17	-19	45	169
	68	-42	-82	108	2	3	51	4	5	8	18	-20	46	169
	67	-41	31	-5	14	6	-7	7	45	7	19	-21	47	169
	66	-40	30	-4	-2	49	8	16	-6	6	20	-22	48	169
	65	-39	29	-3	10	4	-1	40	12	5	21	-23	49	169
	64	-38	28	-2	41	3	14	-2	9	46	-20	-24	50	169
	63	-37	27	-1	78	0	1	2	3	4	3	-25	51	169
	62	-36	28	-2	-52	26	25	24	23	22	23	348	-322	169
	61	-35	440	-34	-33	-32	-31	-30	-29	-28	-27	-26	-27	169
	62	-36	-414	60	59	58	57	56	55	54	53	52	53	169
	169	169	169	169	169	169	169	169	169	169	169	169	169	169

13	mgc	13x13 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT											182	
	32	33	34	35	36	37	38	39	40	41	-211	-14	42	182
	-4	-5	-6	-7	-8	-9	-10	-11	-12	-13	239	-15	43	182
	-493	521	10	11	12	13	14	15	23	12	16	-16	44	182
	69	-41	18	17	16	15	14	13	5	11	17	-17	45	182
	68	-40	-75	103	2	3	56	4	5	10	18	-18	46	182
	67	-39	31	-3	14	6	-7	7	50	9	19	-19	47	182
	66	-38	30	-2	-2	54	8	16	-6	8	20	-20	48	182
	65	-37	29	-1	10	4	-1	45	12	7	21	-21	49	182
	64	-36	28	0	46	3	14	-2	9	41	-13	-22	50	182
	63	-35	27	1	73	2	3	4	5	6	5	-23	51	182
	62	-34	28	0	-45	26	25	24	23	22	23	339	-311	182
	61	-33	431	-32	-31	-30	-29	-28	-27	-26	-25	-24	-25	182
	62	-34	-403	60	59	58	57	56	55	54	53	52	53	182
	182	182	182	182	182	182	182	182	182	182	182	182	182	182

The magic sums are:

- **First example:** $S_{5 \times 5} := 65, S_{9 \times 9} := 117, S_{13 \times 13} := 169$ and $m := 26$.
- **Second example:** $S_{5 \times 5} := 70, S_{9 \times 9} := 126, S_{13 \times 13} := 182$ and $m := 28$.

2.5.2 Flat-Type

Result 2.12. Let's consider an *algebraic magic square* of order 13 with *reduced entries*:

a31	a32	a33	a34	a35	a36	a37	a38	a39	a40	$(13/5)*S-a34-a33-a41-a42-a35-a36-a37-a32-a31-a38-a40-a39$	a41	a42
$2*S/5-a31$	$2*S/5-a32$	$2*S/5-a33$	$2*S/5-a34$	$2*S/5-a35$	$2*S/5-a36$	$2*S/5-a37$	$2*S/5-a38$	$2*S/5-a39$	$2*S/5-a40$	$a34+a33+a41+a42+a35+a36+a37+a32+a31+a38+a40+a39-(11/5)*S$	$2*S/5-a41$	$2*S/5-a42$
$(9/5)*S-a68-a67-a66-a65-a64-a63-a62-a61$	$a68+a67+a66+a65+a64+a63+a62+a61-(7/5)*S$	a9	a10	a11	a12	a13	a14	$(9/5)*S-a9-a10-a11-a12-a13-a14-a15-a16$	a15	a16	$2*S/5-a43$	a43
a68	$2*S/5-a68$	$2*S/5-a9$	$2*S/5-a10$	$2*S/5-a11$	$2*S/5-a12$	$2*S/5-a13$	$2*S/5-a14$	$a9+a10+a11+a12+a13+a14+a15+a16-(7/5)*S$	$2*S/5-a15$	$2*S/5-a16$	$2*S/5-a44$	a44
a67	$2*S/5-a67$	$S-a27-a28-a29-a30$	$a27+a28+a29+a30-(3/5)*S$	a1	a2	$S-a1-a2-a3-a4$	a3	a4	$2*S/5-a23$	a23	$2*S/5-a45$	a45
a66	$2*S/5-a66$	a27	$2*S/5-a27$	$a8-a2+a7$	a5	$a1+a2+a3+a4-a5-a6-a7$	a6	$S-a1-a3-a4-a8$	$2*S/5-a24$	a24	$2*S/5-a46$	a46
a65	$2*S/5-a65$	a28	$2*S/5-a28$	$a2+a3+a4-a5-a7$	$S-a1-a2-a3-a4+a6-a8$	a7	$a7-a2-a3+a5+a8$	$a1+a2+a3-a6-a7$	$2*S/5-a25$	a25	$2*S/5-a47$	a47
a64	$2*S/5-a64$	a29	$2*S/5-a29$	$a7-a3+a5$	$a1-a6+a8$	$a2+a3-a7$	$S-a1-a5-a7-a8$	$a7-a2+a6$	$2*S/5-a26$	a26	$2*S/5-a48$	a48
a63	$2*S/5-a63$	a30	$2*S/5-a30$	$S-a1-a4-a7-a8$	$a3+a4-a5$	$a7-a2-a3+a5+a6$	$a1+a2-a6$	a8	$a23+a24+a25+a26-(3/5)*S$	$S-a23-a24-a25-a26$	$2*S/5-a49$	a49
a62	$2*S/5-a62$	$(2/5)*S+a16-a15-a17$	$2*S/5-a17$	$a15+2*a17+a18+a19+a20+a21+2*a22-a9+a10-(7/5)*S-a16$	$2*S/5-a18$	$2*S/5-a19$	$2*S/5-a20$	$2*S/5-a21$	$2*S/5-a22$	$(2/5)*S+a9-a10-a22$	$2*S/5-a50$	a50
a61	$2*S/5-a61$	$a15+a17-a16$	a17	$(9/5)*S+a16-a15-2*a17-a18-a19-a20-a21-2*a22+a9-a10$	a18	a19	a20	a21	a22	$a10+a22-a9$	$a43+a44+a45+a46+a47+a48+a49+a50-(7/5)*S$	$(9/5)*S-a43-a44-a45-a46-a47-a48-a49-a50$
$(2/5)*S+a42-a41-a60$	$2*S/5-a60$	$a41-a42+2*a60+a32-a31+2*a51+a52+a53+a54+a55+a56+a57+a58+a59-(11/5)*S$	$2*S/5-a59$	$2*S/5-a58$	$2*S/5-a57$	$2*S/5-a56$	$2*S/5-a55$	$2*S/5-a54$	$2*S/5-a53$	$2*S/5-a52$	$2*S/5-a51$	$(2/5)*S+a31-a32-a51$
$a41+a60-a42$	a60	$(13/5)*S-a41+a42-2*a60-a32+a31-2*a51-a52-a53-a54-a55-a56-a57-a58-a59$	a59	a58	a57	a56	a55	a54	a53	a52	a51	$a32+a51-a31$

• Details

It is an **algebraic flat-type** magic square of order 13 composed of two equal sums magic rectangles of orders 2×13 and two equal sums magic rectangles of order 2×9 embedded again with a **flat-type** magic square of order 9. It is again an **algebraic flat-type** magic square of order 9 embedded with a magic square of order 5. In this case the magic sums are $S_{5 \times 5} := S$, $S_{9 \times 9} := \frac{9S}{5}$ and $S_{13 \times 13} := \frac{13S}{5}$, where S is the magic sum of order 5. In this case, $m := \frac{2S}{5}$ is the width of magic rectangles. To avoid decimal entries the magic sums of order 5 should be multiple of 5. See below two examples:

Example 2.12. Let's consider following two examples based on the Result 2.12:

13	mgc	13x13 Inder .J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT											195	13	mgc	13x13 Inder .J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT											221		
	33	34	35	36	37	38	39	40	41	42	-267	43	44	195		33	34	35	36	37	38	39	40	41	42	-241	43	44	221
	-3	-4	-5	-6	-7	-8	-9	-10	-11	-12	297	-13	-14	195		1	0	-1	-2	-3	-4	-5	-6	-7	-8	275	-9	-10	221
	-397	427	11	12	13	14	15	16	19	17	18	-15	45	195		-379	413	11	12	13	14	15	16	37	17	18	-11	45	221
	70	-40	19	18	17	16	15	14	11	13	12	-16	46	195		70	-36	23	22	21	20	19	18	-3	17	16	-12	46	221
	69	-39	-47	77	3	4	57	5	6	5	25	-17	47	195		69	-35	-37	71	3	4	67	5	6	9	25	-13	47	221
	68	-38	29	1	15	7	-6	8	51	4	26	-18	48	195		68	-34	29	5	15	7	-6	8	61	8	26	-14	48	221
	67	-37	30	0	-1	55	9	17	-5	3	27	-19	49	195		67	-33	30	4	-1	65	9	17	-5	7	27	-15	49	221
	66	-36	31	-1	11	5	0	46	13	2	28	-20	50	195		66	-32	31	3	11	5	0	56	13	6	28	-16	50	221
	65	-35	32	-2	47	4	15	-1	10	61	-31	-21	51	195		65	-31	32	2	57	4	15	-1	10	55	-21	-17	51	221
	64	-34	12	11	67	10	9	8	7	6	5	-22	52	195		64	-30	16	15	53	14	13	12	11	10	9	-18	52	221
	63	-33	18	19	-37	20	21	22	23	24	25	283	-253	195		63	-29	18	19	-19	20	21	22	23	24	25	269	-235	221
	-31	-32	525	-31	-30	-29	-28	-27	-26	-25	-24	-23	-24	195		-27	-28	503	-27	-26	-25	-24	-23	-22	-21	-20	-19	-20	221
	61	62	-495	61	60	59	58	57	56	55	54	53	54	195		61	62	-469	61	60	59	58	57	56	55	54	53	54	221
	195	195	195	195	195	195	195	195	195	195	195	195	195	195		221	221	221	221	221	221	221	221	221	221	221	221	221	221

The magic sums are:

- **First example:** $S_{5 \times 5} := 75, S_{9 \times 9} := 135, S_{13 \times 13} := 195$ and $m := 30$.
- **Second example:** $S_{5 \times 5} := 85, S_{9 \times 9} := 153, S_{13 \times 13} := 221$ and $m := 34$.

2.5.3 Cornered

Result 2.13. Let's consider an *algebraic magic square of order 13 with reduced entries*:

$a1+a2-S/3$	$2*S/3-a2$	$2*S/3-a1$	$2*S/3-a3$	$a3$	$2*S/3-a7$	$a7$	$2*S/3-a15$	$a15$	$2*S/3-a27$	$a27$	$2*S/3-a43$	$a43$
$4*S/3-2*a1-a2$	$S/3$	$2*a1+a2-2*S/3$	$2*S/3-a4$	$a4$	$2*S/3-a8$	$a8$	$2*S/3-a16$	$a16$	$2*S/3-a28$	$a28$	$2*S/3-a44$	$a44$
$a1$	$a2$	$S-a1-a2$	$a3+a4-(1/3)*S$	$S-a3-a4$	$2*S/3-a9$	$a9$	$2*S/3-a17$	$a17$	$2*S/3-a29$	$a29$	$2*S/3-a45$	$a45$
$(4/3)*S+a3-a4-a1-a2-a5$	$2*S/3-a5$	$a4+a1+a2+2*a5+2*a6-(5/3)*S-a3$	$2*S/3-a6$	$2*S/3-a6$	$2*S/3-a10$	$a10$	$2*S/3-a18$	$a18$	$2*S/3-a30$	$a30$	$2*S/3-a46$	$a46$
$a4+a1+a2+a5-(2/3)*S-a3$	$a5$	$(7/3)*S+a3-a4-a1-a2-2*a5-2*a6$	$a6$	$a6$	$a7+a8+a9+a10-S$	$(5/3)*S-a7-a8-a9-a10$	$2*S/3-a19$	$a19$	$2*S/3-a31$	$a31$	$2*S/3-a47$	$a47$
$(11/3)*S+a7-a8-2*a4-3*a6-a1-a2-2*a5-a11$	$2*S/3-a11$	$2*S/3-a12$	$2*S/3-a13$	$a8+2*a4+3*a6+a1+a2+2*a5+2*a11+a12+a13+2*a14-(14/3)*S-a7$	$2*S/3-a14$	$2*S/3-a14$	$2*S/3-a20$	$a20$	$2*S/3-a32$	$a32$	$2*S/3-a48$	$a48$
$a8+2*a4+3*a6+a1+a2+2*a5+a11-3*S-a7$	$a11$	$a12$	$a13$	$(16/3)*S+a7-a8-2*a4-3*a6-a1-a2-2*a5-2*a11-a12-a13-2*a14$	$a14$	$a14$	$a15+a16+a17+a18+a19+a20-(5/3)*S$	$(7/3)*S-a15-a16-a17-a18-a19-a20$	$2*S/3-a33$	$a33$	$2*S/3-a49$	$a49$
$S+a15-a16+a9-a10+a6-a13+a12-a21$	$2*S/3-a21$	$2*S/3-a22$	$2*S/3-a23$	$2*S/3-a24$	$2*S/3-a25$	$a16-a9+a10-a6+a13-a12+2*a21+a22+a23+a24+a25+2*a26-(8/3)*S-a15$	$2*S/3-a26$	$2*S/3-a26$	$2*S/3-a34$	$a34$	$2*S/3-a50$	$a50$
$a16-a9+a10-a6+a13-a12+a21-(1/3)*S-a15$	$a21$	$a22$	$a23$	$a24$	$a25$	$(10/3)*S+a15-a16+a9-a10+a6-a13+a12-2*a21-a22-a23-a24-a25-2*a26$	$a26$	$a26$	$a27+a28+a29+a30+a31+a32+a33+a34-(7/3)*S$	$3*S-a27-a28-a29-a30-a31-a32-a33-a34$	$2*S/3-a51$	$a51$
$(22/3)*S+a22-3*a14-a35-2*a11-a10+a17-a13-a9-a18-a12-a1-a2-a23-2*a8-a28-3*a6+a27-2*a5-2*a4$	$2*S/3-a35$	$2*S/3-a36$	$2*S/3-a37$	$2*S/3-a38$	$2*S/3-a39$	$2*S/3-a40$	$2*S/3-a41$	$3*a14+a41+2*a42+2*a35+a36+2*a11+a10-a17+a13+a9+a37+a18+a12+a1+a2+a38+a23+2*a8+a40+a28+3*a6-a27+2*a5+2*a4-(29/3)*S+a39-a22$	$2*S/3-a42$	$2*S/3-a42$	$2*S/3-a52$	$a52$
$3*a14+a35+2*a11+a10-a17+a13+a9+a18+a12+a1+a2+a23+2*a8+a28+3*a6-a27+2*a5+2*a4-(20/3)*S-a22$	$a35$	$a36$	$a37$	$a38$	$a39$	$a40$	$a41$	$a22-3*a14-a41-2*a42-2*a35-a36-2*a11-a10-a17-a13-a9-a37-a18-a12-a1-a2-a38-a23-2*a8-a40-a28-3*a6+a27-2*a5-2*a4+(31/3)*S-a39$	$a42$	$a42$	$a43+a44+a45+a46+a47+a48+a49+a50+a51+a52-3*S$	$(11/3)*S-a43-a44-a45-a46-a47-a48-a49-a50-a51-a52$
$(1/3)*S+a43-a44+a29-a30+a19-a20+a14-a25+a24-a37+a36-a53$	$2*S/3-a53$	$2*S/3-a54$	$2*S/3-a55$	$2*S/3-a56$	$2*S/3-a57$	$2*S/3-a58$	$2*S/3-a59$	$2*S/3-a60$	$2*S/3-a61$	$a44+2*a62+a61+a60+a59+a58+a57+a56+a55+a54+2*a53-a36+a37+a20-a14-a19+a30-a29+a25-a24-(10/3)*S-a43$	$2*S/3-a62$	$2*S/3-a62$
$(1/3)*S-a43+a44-a29+a30-a19+a20-a14+a25-a24+a37-a36+a53$	$a53$	$a54$	$a55$	$a56$	$a57$	$a58$	$a59$	$a60$	$a61$	$4*S+a43-a44-2*a62-a61-a60-a59-a58-a57-a56-a55-a54-2*a53+a36-a37-a20+a14+a19-a30+a29-a25-a24$	$a62$	$a62$

• **Details**

It is an *algebraic cornered*, where the magic squares of orders 13, where the magic squares of order 3, 5, 7, 9 and 11 are at the upper-left corner. In this case, the magic sums are $S_{3 \times 3} := S$, $S_{5 \times 5} := \frac{5S}{3}$, $S_{7 \times 7} := \frac{7S}{3}$, $S_{9 \times 9} := 3S$, $S_{11 \times 11} := 11S/3$ and $S_{13 \times 13} := 13S/3$. The width of magic rectangles is given as $m := \frac{2S}{3}$. In order to avoid decimal entries the magic sum of order 3 should be multiple of 3. Below are two examples.

Example 2.13. Let's consider following two examples based on the Result 2.13:

13	mgc	13x13 Inder .J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT											312	13	mgc	13x13 Inder .J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT											273		
	-21	46	47	45	3	41	7	33	15	21	27	5	43	312		-18	40	41	39	3	35	7	27	15	15	27	-1	43	273
	92	24	-44	44	4	40	8	32	16	20	28	4	44	312		80	21	-38	38	4	34	8	26	16	14	28	-2	44	273
	1	2	69	-17	65	39	9	31	17	19	29	3	45	312		1	2	60	-14	56	33	9	25	17	13	29	-3	45	273
	87	43	-94	42	42	38	10	30	18	18	30	2	46	312		75	37	-79	36	36	32	10	24	18	12	30	-4	46	273
	-39	5	142	6	6	-38	86	29	19	17	31	1	47	312		-33	5	121	6	6	-29	71	23	19	11	31	-5	47	273
	213	37	36	35	-221	34	34	28	20	16	32	0	48	312		180	31	30	29	-179	28	28	22	20	10	32	-6	48	273
	-165	11	12	13	269	14	14	-15	63	15	33	-1	49	312		-138	11	12	13	221	14	14	0	42	9	33	-7	49	273
	54	27	26	25	24	23	-7	22	22	14	34	-2	50	312		45	21	20	19	18	17	17	16	16	8	34	-8	50	273
	-6	21	22	23	24	25	55	26	26	76	-28	-3	51	312		-3	21	22	23	24	25	25	26	26	97	-55	-9	51	273
	327	13	12	11	10	9	8	7	-145	6	6	-4	52	312		261	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	-58	0	0	-10	52	273
	-279	35	36	37	38	39	40	41	193	42	42	259	-211	312		-219	35	36	37	38	39	40	41	100	42	42	286	-244	273
	-20	-5	-6	-7	-8	-9	-10	-11	-12	-13	441	-14	-14	312		-23	-11	-12	-13	-14	-15	-16	-17	-18	-19	471	-20	-20	273
	68	53	54	55	56	57	58	59	60	61	-393	62	62	312		65	53	54	55	56	57	58	59	60	61	-429	62	62	273
	312	312	312	312	312	312	312	312	312	312	312	312	312	312		273	273	273	273	273	273	273	273	273	273	273	273	273	

The magic sums are:

- **First example:** $S_{3 \times 3} := 72, S_{5 \times 5} := 120, S_{7 \times 7} := 168, S_{9 \times 9} := 216, S_{11 \times 11} := 264, S_{13 \times 13} := 312$ and $m := 48$.
- **Second example:** $S_{3 \times 3} := 63, S_{5 \times 5} := 105, S_{7 \times 7} := 147, S_{9 \times 9} := 189, S_{11 \times 11} := 231, S_{13 \times 13} := 273$ and $m := 42$.

2.6 Double-Digit Algebraic Magic Squares of Order 15

Below are three different ways of writing magic square of order 15, i.e., **cyclic**, **flat** and **cornered**.

2.6.1 Cyclic-Type

Result 2.14. Let's consider an *algebraic magic square of order 15 with reduced entries*:

a48	a49	a50	a51	a52	a53	a54	a55	a56	a57	a58	a59	(13/3)*S-a59-a58-a57-a56-a55-a54-a53-a52-a51-a50-a49-a48	(2/3)*S-a60	a60
(2/3)*S-a48	(2/3)*S-a49	(2/3)*S-a50	(2/3)*S-a51	(2/3)*S-a52	(2/3)*S-a53	(2/3)*S-a54	(2/3)*S-a55	(2/3)*S-a56	(2/3)*S-a57	(2/3)*S-a58	(2/3)*S-a59	a59+a58+a57+a56+a55+a54+a53+a52+a51+a50+a49+a48-(11/3)*S	(2/3)*S-a61	a61
(13/3)*S-a92-a93-a89-a90-a91-a88-a84-a85-a86-2*a83+a60-a87-	a92+a93+a89+a90+a91+a88+a84+a85+a86+2*a83-a60+a87+(11/3)*S	a17	a18	a19	a20	a21	a22	a23	a24	3*S-a17-a18-a19-a20-a21-a22-a23-a24	(2/3)*S-a25	a25	(2/3)*S-a62	a62
a93	(2/3)*S-a93	(2/3)*S-a17	(2/3)*S-a18	(2/3)*S-a19	(2/3)*S-a20	(2/3)*S-a21	(2/3)*S-a22	(2/3)*S-a23	(2/3)*S-a24	a17+a18+a19+a20+a21+a22+a23+a24-(7/3)*S	(2/3)*S-a26	a26	(2/3)*S-a63	a63
a92	(2/3)*S-a92	3*S-a47-a46-a45-a44-a43-a42-2*a41+a25-a26	a47+a46+a45+a44+a43+a42+2*a41-a25+a26-(7/3)*S	a3	a4	a5	a6	(5/3)*S-a3-a4-a5-a6	(2/3)*S-a7	a7	(2/3)*S-a27	a27	(2/3)*S-a64	a64
a91	(2/3)*S-a91	a47	(2/3)*S-a47	(2/3)*S-a3	(2/3)*S-a4	(2/3)*S-a5	(2/3)*S-a6	a3+a4+a5+a6-S	(2/3)*S-a8	a8	(2/3)*S-a28	a28	(2/3)*S-a65	a65
a90	(2/3)*S-a90	a46	(2/3)*S-a46	(5/3)*S+a7-a8-2*a14-a15-a16	a8+2*a14+a15+a16-S-a7	a1+a2-S/3	2*S/3-a2	2*S/3-a1	(2/3)*S-a9	a9	(2/3)*S-a29	a29	(2/3)*S-a66	a66
a89	(2/3)*S-a89	a45	(2/3)*S-a45	a16	(2/3)*S-a16	4*S/3-2*a1-a2	S/3	2*a1+a2-2*S/3	(2/3)*S-a10	a10	(2/3)*S-a30	a30	(2/3)*S-a67	a67
a88	(2/3)*S-a88	a44	(2/3)*S-a44	a15	(2/3)*S-a15	a1	a2	S-a1-a2	a7+a8+a9+a10-S	(5/3)*S-a7-a8-a9-a10	(2/3)*S-a31	a31	(2/3)*S-a68	a68
a87	(2/3)*S-a87	a43	(2/3)*S-a43	a14	(2/3)*S-a14	a4+2*a11+a12+a13-S-a3	(2/3)*S-a13	(2/3)*S-a12	(2/3)*S-a11	(2/3)*S+a3-a4-a11	(2/3)*S-a32	a32	(2/3)*S-a69	a69
a86	(2/3)*S-a86	a42	(2/3)*S-a42	a8+a14-a7	(2/3)*S+a7-a8-a14	(5/3)*S+a3-a4-2*a11-a12-a13	a13	a12	a11	a4+a11-a3	a25+a26+a27+a28+a29+a30+a31+a32-(7/3)*S	3*S-a25-a26-a27-a28-a29-a30-a31-a32	(2/3)*S-a70	a70
a85	(2/3)*S-a85	a41	(2/3)*S-a41	a39+a38+a37+a36+a35+a34+2*a33-a17+a18-(7/3)*S	(2/3)*S-a39	(2/3)*S-a38	(2/3)*S-a37	(2/3)*S-a36	(2/3)*S-a35	(2/3)*S-a34	(2/3)*S-a33	(2/3)*S+a17-a18-a33	(2/3)*S-a71	a71
a84	(2/3)*S-a84	a26+a41-a25	(2/3)*S+a25-a26-a41	3*S-a39-a38-a37-a36-a35-a34-2*a33+a17-a18	a39	a38	a37	a36	a35	a34	a33	a18+a33-a17	a71+a70+a69+a68+a67+a66+a65+a64+a63+a62+a61-(11/3)*S	(13/3)*S-a71-a70-a69-a68-a67-a66-a65-a64-a63-a62-a61
a83	(2/3)*S-a83	2*a72+a73+a74+a75+a76+a77+a78+a79+a80+a81+a82-a48+a49-(11/3)*S	(2/3)*S-a82	(2/3)*S-a81	(2/3)*S-a80	(2/3)*S-a79	(2/3)*S-a78	(2/3)*S-a77	(2/3)*S-a76	(2/3)*S-a75	(2/3)*S-a74	(2/3)*S-a73	(2/3)*S-a72	(2/3)*S+a48-a49-a72
a61+a83-a60	(2/3)*S+a60-a61-a83	(13/3)*S-2*a72-a73-a74-a75-a76-a77-a78-a79-a80-a81-a82+a48-a49	a82	a81	a80	a79	a78	a77	a76	a75	a74	a73	a72	a49+a72-a48

• **Details**

It is an **algebraic cyclic-type** magic square of order 15 composed of four equal sums magic rectangles of orders 2×13 embedded with a magic square of order 11. It is again composed of four equal sums magic rectangles of order 2×9 having a magic square of order 3 in the middle. In this case, the magic sums are $S_{3 \times 3} := S$, $S_{7 \times 7} := \frac{7S}{3}$, $S_{11 \times 11} := \frac{11S}{3}$ and $S_{15 \times 15} := 5S$. The width of magic rectangles is given as $m := \frac{2S}{3}$. In order to avoid decimal entries the magic sum of order 3 should be multiple of 3. Below are two examples.

Example 2.14. Let's consider following two examples based on the Result 2.14:

15	mgc	15x15 https://numbers-magic.com/ https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT														315
49	50	51	52	53	54	55	56	57	58	59	60	-381	-19	61	315	
-7	-8	-9	-10	-11	-12	-13	-14	-15	-16	-17	-18	423	-20	62	315	
-791	833	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	17	16	26	-21	63	315	
94	-52	24	23	22	21	20	19	18	17	25	15	27	-22	64	315	
93	-51	-169	211	4	5	6	7	83	34	8	14	28	-23	65	315	
92	-50	48	-6	38	37	36	35	-41	33	9	13	29	-24	66	315	
91	-49	47	-5	41	1	-16	39	40	32	10	12	30	-25	67	315	
90	-48	46	-4	17	25	77	21	-35	31	11	11	31	-26	68	315	
89	-47	45	-3	16	26	2	3	58	-25	67	10	32	-27	69	315	
88	-46	44	-2	15	27	-11	28	29	30	29	9	33	-28	70	315	
87	-45	43	-1	16	26	53	14	13	12	13	89	-47	-29	71	315	
86	-44	42	0	147	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	7	-30	72	315	
85	-43	43	-1	-105	40	39	38	37	36	35	34	35	567	-525	315	
84	-42	701	-41	-40	-39	-38	-37	-36	-35	-34	-33	-32	-31	-32	315	
85	-43	-659	83	82	81	80	79	78	77	76	75	74	73	74	315	
315	315	315	315	315	315	315	315	315	315	315	315	315	315	315	315	

15	mgc	15x15 https://numbers-magic.com/ https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT														360
49	50	51	52	53	54	55	56	57	58	59	60	-342	-13	61	360	
-1	-2	-3	-4	-5	-6	-7	-8	-9	-10	-11	-12	390	-14	62	360	
-752	800	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	44	22	26	-15	63	360	
94	-46	30	29	28	27	26	25	24	23	4	21	27	-16	64	360	
93	-45	-142	190	4	5	6	7	98	40	8	20	28	-17	65	360	
92	-44	48	0	44	43	42	41	-50	39	9	19	29	-18	66	360	
91	-43	47	1	56	-8	-19	45	46	38	10	18	30	-19	67	360	
90	-42	46	2	17	31	89	24	-41	37	11	17	31	-20	68	360	
89	-41	45	3	16	32	2	3	67	-34	82	16	32	-21	69	360	
88	-40	44	4	15	33	-20	34	35	36	35	15	33	-22	70	360	
87	-39	43	5	16	32	68	14	13	12	13	68	-20	-23	71	360	
86	-38	42	6	126	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	13	-24	72	360	
85	-37	43	5	-78	40	39	38	37	36	35	34	35	534	-486	360	
84	-36	668	-35	-34	-33	-32	-31	-30	-29	-28	-27	-26	-25	-26	360	
85	-37	-620	83	82	81	80	79	78	77	76	75	74	73	74	360	
360	360	360	360	360	360	360	360	360	360	360	360	360	360	360	360	

The magic sums are:

- *First example:* $S_{3 \times 3} := 63, S_{7 \times 7} := 147, S_{11 \times 11} := 231, S_{15 \times 15} := 315$ and $m := 42$.
- *Second example:* $S_{3 \times 3} := 72, S_{7 \times 7} := 168, S_{11 \times 11} := 264, S_{15 \times 15} := 360$ and $m := 48$.

2.6.2 Flat-Type

Result 2.15. Let's consider an *algebraic magic square of order 15 with reduced entries*:

a47	a48	a49	a50	a51	a52	a53	a54	a55	a56	a57	a58	5*S-a49-a48-a60-a51-a47-a52-a53-a54-a55-a56-a57-a58-a59-a50	a59	a60
(2/3)*S-a47	(2/3)*S-a48	(2/3)*S-a49	(2/3)*S-a50	(2/3)*S-a51	(2/3)*S-a52	(2/3)*S-a53	(2/3)*S-a54	(2/3)*S-a55	(2/3)*S-a56	(2/3)*S-a57	(2/3)*S-a58	a49+a48+a60+a51+a47+a52+a53+a54+a55+a56+a57+a58+a59+a50-(13/3)*S	(2/3)*S-a59	(2/3)*S-a60
(11/3)*S-a92-a91-a90-a89-a88-a87-a86-a85-a84-a83	a92+a91+a90+a89+a88+a87+a86+a85+a84+a83-3*S	a17	a18	a19	a20	a21	a22	a23	a24	(11/3)*S-a17-a18-a19-a20-a21-a22-a23-a24-a25-a26	a25	a26	(2/3)*S-a61	a61
a92	(2/3)*S-a92	(2/3)*S-a17	(2/3)*S-a18	(2/3)*S-a19	(2/3)*S-a20	(2/3)*S-a21	(2/3)*S-a22	(2/3)*S-a23	(2/3)*S-a24	a17+a18+a19+a20+a21+a22+a23+a24+a25+a26-3*S	(2/3)*S-a25	(2/3)*S-a26	(2/3)*S-a62	a62
a91	(2/3)*S-a91	(7/3)*S-a46-a45-a44-a43-a42-a41	a46+a45+a44+a43+a42+a41-(5/3)*S	a3	a4	a5	a6	(7/3)*S-a3-a4-a5-a6-a7-a8	a7	a8	(2/3)*S-a27	a27	(2/3)*S-a63	a63
a90	(2/3)*S-a90	a46	(2/3)*S-a46	(2/3)*S-a3	(2/3)*S-a4	(2/3)*S-a5	(2/3)*S-a6	a3+a4+a5+a6+a7+a8-(5/3)*S	(2/3)*S-a7	(2/3)*S-a8	(2/3)*S-a28	a28	(2/3)*S-a64	a64
a89	(2/3)*S-a89	a45	(2/3)*S-a45	S-a15-a16	a15+a16-(1/3)*S	a1+a2-S/3	2*S/3-a2	2*S/3-a1	(2/3)*S-a13	a13	(2/3)*S-a29	a29	(2/3)*S-a65	a65
a88	(2/3)*S-a88	a44	(2/3)*S-a44	a16	(2/3)*S-a16	4*S/3-2*a1-a2	S/3	2*a1+a2-2*S/3	(2/3)*S-a14	a14	(2/3)*S-a30	a30	(2/3)*S-a66	a66
a87	(2/3)*S-a87	a43	(2/3)*S-a43	a15	(2/3)*S-a15	a1	a2	S-a1-a2	a13+a14-(1/3)*S	S-a13-a14	(2/3)*S-a31	a31	(2/3)*S-a67	a67
a86	(2/3)*S-a86	a42	(2/3)*S-a42	(2/3)*S+a8-a7-a9	(2/3)*S-a9	a7+2*a9+a10+a11+2*a12-a3+a4-(5/3)*S-a8	(2/3)*S-a10	(2/3)*S-a11	(2/3)*S-a12	(2/3)*S+a3-a4-a12	(2/3)*S-a32	a32	(2/3)*S-a68	a68
a85	(2/3)*S-a85	a41	(2/3)*S-a41	a7+a9-a8	a9	(7/3)*S+a8-a7-2*a9-a10-a11-2*a12+a3-a4	a10	a11	a12	a4+a12-a3	a27+a28+a29+a30+a31+a32-(5/3)*S	(7/3)*S-a27-a28-a29-a30-a31-a32	(2/3)*S-a69	a69
a84	(2/3)*S-a84	(2/3)*S+a26-a25-a40	(2/3)*S-a40	a34+2*a33+a35+a36-a17+a37+a18+a38-a26+a25+2*a40+a39-3*S	(2/3)*S-a39	(2/3)*S-a38	(2/3)*S-a37	(2/3)*S-a36	(2/3)*S-a35	(2/3)*S-a34	(2/3)*S-a33	(2/3)*S+a17-a18-a33	(2/3)*S-a70	a70
a83	(2/3)*S-a83	a25+a40-a26	a40	(11/3)*S-a34-2*a33-a35-a36+a17-a37-a18-a38+a26-a25-2*a40-a39	a39	a38	a37	a36	a35	a34	a33	a18+a33-a17	a61+a62+a63+a64+a65+a66+a67+a68+a69+a70-3*S	(11/3)*S-a61-a62-a63-a64-a65-a66-a67-a68-a69-a70
(2/3)*S+a60-a59-a82	(2/3)*S-a82	a48+a78+a79+a72+a73-a60+a74+a81+a75+a76+a77+2*a71-a47+2*a82+a80+a59-(13/3)*S	(2/3)*S-a81	(2/3)*S-a80	(2/3)*S-a79	(2/3)*S-a78	(2/3)*S-a77	(2/3)*S-a76	(2/3)*S-a75	(2/3)*S-a74	(2/3)*S-a73	(2/3)*S-a72	(2/3)*S-a71	(2/3)*S+a47-a48-a71
a59+a82-a60	a82	5*S-a48-a78-a79-a72-a73+a60-a74-a81-a75-a76-a77-2*a71+a47-2*a82-a80-a59	a81	a80	a79	a78	a77	a76	a75	a74	a73	a72	a71	a48+a71-a47

• **Details**

It is an **algebraic flat-type** magic square of order 15 composed of two equal sums magic rectangles of orders 2×15 and two equal sums magic rectangles of order 2×11 embedded again with a **flat-type** magic square of order 11 and so on. In this case, the magic sums are $S_{3 \times 3} := S$, $S_{7 \times 7} := \frac{7S}{3}$, $S_{11 \times 11} := \frac{11S}{3}$ and $S_{15 \times 15} := 5S$. The width of magic rectangles is given as $m := \frac{2S}{3}$. In order to avoid decimal entries the magic sum of order 3 should be multiple of 3. Below are two examples.

Example 2.15. Let's consider following two examples based on the Result 2.15:

15	mgc	15x15 https://numbers-magic.com/ https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT														465
47	48	49	50	51	52	53	54	55	56	57	58	-284	59	60	465	
15	14	13	12	11	10	9	8	7	6	5	4	346	3	2	465	
-534	596	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	126	25	26	1	61	465	
92	-30	45	44	43	42	41	40	39	38	-64	37	36	0	62	465	
91	-29	-44	106	3	4	5	6	184	7	8	35	27	-1	63	465	
90	-28	46	16	59	58	57	56	-122	55	54	34	28	-2	64	465	
89	-27	45	17	62	0	-28	60	61	49	13	33	29	-3	65	465	
88	-26	44	18	16	46	120	31	-58	48	14	32	30	-4	66	465	
87	-25	43	19	15	47	1	2	90	-4	66	31	31	-5	67	465	
86	-24	42	20	54	53	-92	52	51	50	49	30	32	-6	68	465	
85	-23	41	21	8	9	154	10	11	12	13	22	40	-7	69	465	
84	-22	23	22	86	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	28	-8	70	465	
83	-21	39	40	-24	39	38	37	36	35	34	33	34	376	-314	465	
-19	-20	668	-19	-18	-17	-16	-15	-14	-13	-12	-11	-10	-9	-10	465	
81	82	-606	81	80	79	78	77	76	75	74	73	72	71	72	465	
465	465	465	465	465	465	465	465	465	465	465	465	465	465	465	465	

15	mgc	15x15 https://numbers-magic.com/ https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT														510
47	48	49	50	51	52	53	54	55	56	57	58	-239	59	60	510	
21	20	19	18	17	16	15	14	13	12	11	10	307	9	8	510	
-501	569	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	159	25	26	7	61	510	
92	-24	51	50	49	48	47	46	45	44	-91	43	42	6	62	510	
91	-23	-23	91	3	4	5	6	205	7	8	41	27	5	63	510	
90	-22	46	22	65	64	63	62	-137	61	60	40	28	4	64	510	
89	-21	45	23	71	-3	-31	66	67	55	13	39	29	3	65	510	
88	-20	44	24	16	52	132	34	-64	54	14	38	30	2	66	510	
87	-19	43	25	15	53	1	2	99	-7	75	37	31	1	67	510	
86	-18	42	26	60	59	-107	58	57	56	55	36	32	0	68	510	
85	-17	41	27	8	9	175	10	11	12	13	7	61	-1	69	510	
84	-16	29	28	59	29	30	31	32	33	34	35	34	-2	70	510	
83	-15	39	40	9	39	38	37	36	35	34	33	34	349	-281	510	
-13	-14	629	-13	-12	-11	-10	-9	-8	-7	-6	-5	-4	-3	-4	510	
81	82	-561	81	80	79	78	77	76	75	74	73	72	71	72	510	
510	510	510	510	510	510	510	510	510	510	510	510	510	510	510	510	

The magic sums are:

- **First example:** $S_{3 \times 3} := 93, S_{7 \times 7} := 341, S_{11 \times 11} := 231, S_{15 \times 15} := 465$ and $m := 62$.
- **Second example:** $S_{3 \times 3} := 102, S_{7 \times 7} := 238, S_{11 \times 11} := 374, S_{15 \times 15} := 510$ and $m := 68$.

2.6.3 Cornered

Result 2.16. Let's consider an *algebraic magic square of order 15 with reduced entries*:

$a_1+a_2-S/3$	$2^*S/3-a_2$	$2^*S/3-a_1$	$2^*S/3-a_3$	a_3	$2^*S/3-a_7$	a_7	$2^*S/3-a_{15}$	a_{15}	$2^*S/3-a_{27}$	a_{27}	$2^*S/3-a_{43}$	a_{43}	$2^*S/3-a_{63}$	a_{63}
$4^*S/3-2^*a_1-a_2$	$S/3$	$2^*a_1+a_2-2^*S/3$	$2^*S/3-a_4$	a_4	$2^*S/3-a_8$	a_8	$2^*S/3-a_{16}$	a_{16}	$2^*S/3-a_{28}$	a_{28}	$2^*S/3-a_{44}$	a_{44}	$2^*S/3-a_{64}$	a_{64}
a_1	a_2	$S-a_1-a_2$	$a_3+a_4-(1/3)^*S$	$S-a_3-a_4$	$2^*S/3-a_9$	a_9	$2^*S/3-a_{17}$	a_{17}	$2^*S/3-a_{29}$	a_{29}	$2^*S/3-a_{45}$	a_{45}	$2^*S/3-a_{65}$	a_{65}
$(4/3)^*S+a_3-a_4-a_1-a_2-a_5$	$2^*S/3-a_5$	$a_4+a_1+a_2+2^*a_5+2^*a_6-(5/3)^*S-a_3$	$2^*S/3-a_6$	$2^*S/3-a_6$	$2^*S/3-a_{10}$	a_{10}	$2^*S/3-a_{18}$	a_{18}	$2^*S/3-a_{30}$	a_{30}	$2^*S/3-a_{46}$	a_{46}	$2^*S/3-a_{66}$	a_{66}
$a_4+a_1+a_2+a_5-(2/3)^*S-a_3$	a_5	$(7/3)^*S+a_3-a_4-a_1-a_2-2^*a_5-2^*a_6$	a_6	a_6	$a_7+a_8+a_9+a_{10}-S$	$(5/3)^*S-a_7-a_8-a_9-a_{10}$	$2^*S/3-a_{19}$	a_{19}	$2^*S/3-a_{31}$	a_{31}	$2^*S/3-a_{47}$	a_{47}	$2^*S/3-a_{67}$	a_{67}
$(11/3)^*S+a_7-a_8-2^*a_4-3^*a_6-a_1-a_2-2^*a_5-a_{11}$	$2^*S/3-a_{11}$	$2^*S/3-a_{12}$	$2^*S/3-a_{13}$	$a_8+2^*a_4+3^*a_6+a_1+a_2+2^*a_5+2^*a_{11}+a_{12}+a_{13}+2^*a_{14}-(14/3)^*S-a_7$	$2^*S/3-a_{14}$	$2^*S/3-a_{14}$	$2^*S/3-a_{20}$	a_{20}	$2^*S/3-a_{32}$	a_{32}	$2^*S/3-a_{48}$	a_{48}	$2^*S/3-a_{68}$	a_{68}
$a_8+2^*a_4+3^*a_6+a_1+a_2+2^*a_5+a_{11}-3^*S-a_7$	a_{11}	a_{12}	a_{13}	$(16/3)^*S+a_7-a_8-2^*a_4-3^*a_6-a_1-a_2-2^*a_5-2^*a_{11}-a_{12}-a_{13}-2^*a_{14}$	a_{14}	a_{14}	$a_{15}+a_{16}+a_{17}+a_{18}+a_{19}+a_{20}-(5/3)^*S$	$(7/3)^*S-a_{15}-a_{16}-a_{17}-a_{18}-a_{19}-a_{20}$	$2^*S/3-a_{33}$	a_{33}	$2^*S/3-a_{49}$	a_{49}	$2^*S/3-a_{69}$	a_{69}
$S+a_{15}-a_{16}+a_9-a_{10}+a_6-a_{13}+a_{12}-a_{21}$	$2^*S/3-a_{21}$	$2^*S/3-a_{22}$	$2^*S/3-a_{23}$	$2^*S/3-a_{24}$	$2^*S/3-a_{25}$	$a_{16}-a_9+a_{10}-a_6+a_{13}-a_{12}+2^*a_{21}+a_{22}+a_{23}+a_{24}+a_{25}+2^*a_{26}-(8/3)^*S-a_{15}$	$2^*S/3-a_{26}$	$2^*S/3-a_{26}$	$2^*S/3-a_{34}$	a_{34}	$2^*S/3-a_{50}$	a_{50}	$2^*S/3-a_{70}$	a_{70}
$a_{16}-a_9+a_{10}-a_6+a_{13}-a_{12}+a_{21}-(1/3)^*S-a_{15}$	a_{21}	a_{22}	a_{23}	a_{24}	a_{25}	$(10/3)^*S+a_{15}-a_{16}+a_9-a_{10}+a_6-a_{13}+a_{12}-2^*a_{21}-a_{22}-a_{23}-a_{24}-a_{25}-2^*a_{26}$	a_{26}	a_{26}	$a_{27}+a_{28}+a_{29}+a_{30}+a_{31}+a_{32}+a_{33}+a_{34}-(7/3)^*S$	$3^*S-a_{27}-a_{28}-a_{29}-a_{30}-a_{31}-a_{32}-a_{33}-a_{34}$	$2^*S/3-a_{51}$	a_{51}	$2^*S/3-a_{71}$	a_{71}
$(22/3)^*S+a_{22}-3^*a_{14}-a_{35}-2^*a_{11}-a_{10}+a_{17}-a_{13}-a_9-a_{18}-a_{12}-a_1-a_2-a_{23}-2^*a_8-a_{28}-3^*a_6+a_{27}-2^*a_5-2^*a_4$	$2^*S/3-a_{35}$	$2^*S/3-a_{36}$	$2^*S/3-a_{37}$	$2^*S/3-a_{38}$	$2^*S/3-a_{39}$	$2^*S/3-a_{40}$	$2^*S/3-a_{41}$	$3^*a_{14}+a_{41}+2^*a_{42}+2^*a_3+5+a_{36}+2^*a_{11}+a_{10}-a_{17}+a_{13}+a_9+a_{37}+a_{18}+a_{12}+a_1+a_2+a_{38}+a_{23}+2^*a_8+a_{40}+a_{28}+3^*a_6-a_{27}+2^*a_5+2^*a_4-(29/3)^*S+a_{39}-a_{22}$	$2^*S/3-a_{42}$	$2^*S/3-a_{42}$	$2^*S/3-a_{52}$	a_{52}	$2^*S/3-a_{72}$	a_{72}
$3^*a_{14}+a_{35}+2^*a_{11}+a_{10}-a_{17}+a_{13}+a_9-a_{18}+a_{12}+a_1+a_2+a_{23}+2^*a_8+a_{28}+3^*a_6-a_{27}+2^*a_5+2^*a_4-(20/3)^*S-a_{22}$	a_{35}	a_{36}	a_{37}	a_{38}	a_{39}	a_{40}	a_{41}	a_{42}	a_{42}	a_{42}	$a_{43}+a_{44}+a_{45}+a_{46}+a_{47}+a_{48}+a_{49}+a_{50}+a_{51}+a_{52}-3^*S$	$(11/3)^*S-a_{43}-a_{44}-a_{45}-a_{46}-a_{47}-a_{48}-a_{49}-a_{50}-a_{51}-a_{52}$	$2^*S/3-a_{73}$	a_{73}
$(1/3)^*S+a_{43}-a_{44}+a_{29}-a_{30}+a_{19}-a_{20}+a_{14}-a_{25}+a_{24}-a_{37}+a_{36}-a_{53}$	$2^*S/3-a_{53}$	$2^*S/3-a_{54}$	$2^*S/3-a_{55}$	$2^*S/3-a_{56}$	$2^*S/3-a_{57}$	$2^*S/3-a_{58}$	$2^*S/3-a_{59}$	$2^*S/3-a_{60}$	$2^*S/3-a_{61}$	$a_{44}+2^*a_{62}+a_{61}+a_{60}+a_{59}+a_{58}+a_{57}+a_{56}+a_{55}+a_{54}+2^*a_{53}-a_{36}+a_{37}+a_{20}-a_{14}-a_{19}+a_{30}-a_{29}+a_{25}-a_{24}-(10/3)^*S-a_{43}$	$2^*S/3-a_{62}$	$2^*S/3-a_{62}$	$2^*S/3-a_{74}$	a_{74}
$(1/3)^*S-a_{43}+a_{44}-a_{29}+a_{30}-a_{19}+a_{20}-a_{14}+a_{25}-a_{24}+a_{37}-a_{36}+a_{53}$	a_{53}	a_{54}	a_{55}	a_{56}	a_{57}	a_{58}	a_{59}	a_{60}	a_{61}	a_{61}	a_{62}	a_{62}	$a_{63}+a_{64}+a_{65}+a_6+6+a_{67}+a_{68}+a_{69}+a_{70}+a_{71}+a_{72}+a_{73}+a_{74}-(11/3)^*S$	$(13/3)^*S-a_{63}-a_{64}-a_{65}-a_{66}-a_{67}-a_{68}-a_{69}-a_{70}-a_{71}-a_{72}-a_{73}-a_{74}$
$6^*S-a_{75}-a_{55}+a_{54}+a_{38}-a_{39}-a_{23}-a_{24}-a_{25}+a_{12}-2^*a_{21}-a_{22}+a_9-a_{10}-a_{13}-3^*a_{26}-a_{20}-2^*a_{16}-a_{17}-a_{18}-a_{19}-a_{32}+a_{31}+a_{45}-a_{46}+a_6-a_{64}+a_{63}$	$2^*S/3-a_{75}$	$2^*S/3-a_{76}$	$2^*S/3-a_{77}$	$2^*S/3-a_{78}$	$2^*S/3-a_{79}$	$2^*S/3-a_{80}$	$2^*S/3-a_{81}$	$2^*S/3-a_{82}$	$2^*S/3-a_{83}$	$2^*S/3-a_{84}$	$2^*S/3-a_{85}$	$a_{82}+a_{81}+a_{80}+a_{79}+a_{78}+a_{77}+a_{76}-(29/3)^*S+2^*a_{75}+a_{55}-a_{54}-a_{38}+a_{39}+a_{23}+a_{24}+a_{25}-a_{12}+2^*a_{21}+a_{22}-a_9+a_{10}+a_{13}+3^*a_{26}+a_{20}+2^*a_{16}+a_{17}+a_{18}+a_{19}+a_{32}-a_{31}-a_{45}+a_{46}-a_6+2^*a_{64}+a_{65}+a_{64}+a_{63}+a_6$	$2^*S/3-a_{86}$	$2^*S/3-a_{86}$
$a_{75}+a_{55}-a_{54}-a_{38}+a_{39}+a_{23}+a_{24}+a_{25}-a_{12}+2^*a_{21}+a_{22}-a_9+a_{10}+a_{13}+3^*a_{26}+a_{20}+2^*a_{16}+a_{17}+a_{18}+a_{19}+a_{32}-a_{31}-a_{45}+a_{46}-a_6+a_{64}-a_{63}-(16/3)^*S$	a_{75}	a_{76}	a_{77}	a_{78}	a_{79}	a_{80}	a_{81}	a_{82}	a_{83}	a_{84}	a_{85}	$(31/3)^*S-2^*a_{75}-a_{55}+a_{54}+a_{38}-a_{39}-a_{23}-a_{24}-a_{25}+a_{12}-2^*a_{21}-a_{22}+a_9-a_{10}-a_{13}-3^*a_{26}-a_{20}-2^*a_{16}-a_{17}-a_{18}-a_{19}-a_{32}+a_{31}+a_{45}-a_{46}+a_6-2^*a_{64}-a_{65}-a_{64}-a_{63}-a_{63}-a_{81}-a_{80}-a_{79}-a_{78}-a_{77}-a_{76}$	a_{86}	a_{86}

• Details

It is an **algebraic cornered**, where the magic squares of orders 15, where the magic squares of order 3, 5, 7, 9, 11 and 13 are at the upper-left corner. In this case, the magic sums are $S_{3 \times 3} := S$, $S_{5 \times 5} := \frac{5S}{3}$, $S_{7 \times 7} := \frac{7S}{3}$, $S_{9 \times 9} := 3S$, $S_{11 \times 11} := 11S/3$, $S_{13 \times 13} := 13S/3$ and $S_{13 \times 15} := 15S/3$. The width of magic rectangles is given as $m := \frac{2S}{3}$. In order to avoid decimal entries the magic sum of order 3 should be multiple of 3. Below are two examples.

Example 2.16. Let's consider following two examples based on the Result 2.16:

15	mgc	15x15 https://numbers-magic.com/ https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT														405	15	mgc	15x15 https://numbers-magic.com/ https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT														450
	-20	50	51	49	5	45	9	37	17	25	29	9	45	-11	65	405		-23	56	57	55	5	51	9	43	17	31	29	15	45	-5	65	450
	98	27	-44	48	6	44	10	36	18	24	30	8	46	-12	66	405		110	30	-50	54	6	50	10	42	18	30	30	14	46	-6	66	450
	3	4	74	-16	70	43	11	35	19	23	31	7	47	-13	67	405		3	4	83	-19	79	49	11	41	19	29	31	13	47	-7	67	450
	93	47	-97	46	46	42	12	34	20	22	32	6	48	-14	68	405		105	53	-112	52	52	48	12	40	20	28	32	12	48	-8	68	450
	-39	7	151	8	8	-39	93	33	21	21	33	5	49	-15	69	405		-45	7	172	8	8	-48	108	39	21	27	33	11	49	-9	69	450
	226	41	40	39	-233	38	38	32	22	20	34	4	50	-16	70	405		259	47	46	45	-275	44	44	38	22	26	34	10	50	-10	70	450
	-172	13	14	15	287	16	16	-18	72	19	35	3	51	-17	71	405		-199	13	14	15	335	16	16	-33	93	25	35	9	51	-11	71	450
	63	31	30	29	28	27	-17	26	26	18	36	2	52	-18	72	405		72	37	36	35	34	33	-41	32	32	24	36	8	52	-12	72	450
	-9	23	24	25	26	27	71	28	28	71	-17	1	53	-19	73	405		-12	23	24	25	26	27	101	28	28	50	10	7	53	-13	73	450
	351	17	16	15	14	13	12	11	-172	10	10	0	54	-20	74	405		417	23	22	21	20	19	18	17	-259	16	16	6	54	-14	74	450
	-297	37	38	39	40	41	42	43	226	44	44	252	-198	-21	75	405		-357	37	38	39	40	41	42	43	319	44	44	225	-165	-15	75	450
	-17	-1	-2	-3	-4	-5	-6	-7	-8	-9	433	-10	-10	-22	76	405		-14	5	4	3	2	1	0	-1	-2	-3	403	-4	-4	-16	76	450
	71	55	56	57	58	59	60	61	62	63	-379	64	64	549	-495	405		74	55	56	57	58	59	60	61	62	63	-343	64	64	516	-456	450
	60	-23	-24	-25	-26	-27	-28	-29	-30	-31	-32	-33	721	-34	-34	405		114	-17	-18	-19	-20	-21	-22	-23	-24	-25	-26	-27	634	-28	-28	450
	-6	77	78	79	80	81	82	83	84	85	86	87	-667	88	88	405		-54	77	78	79	80	81	82	83	84	85	86	87	-574	88	88	450
	405	405	405	405	405	405	405	405	405	405	405	405	405	405	405	405		450	450	450	450	450	450	450	450	450	450	450	450	450	450	450	

The magic sums are:

- **First example:** $S_{3 \times 3} := 81, S_{5 \times 5} := 135, S_{7 \times 7} := 189, S_{9 \times 9} := 243, S_{11 \times 11} := 297, S_{13 \times 13} := 351, S_{15 \times 15} := 405$ and $m := 54$.
- **Second example:** $S_{3 \times 3} := 90, S_{5 \times 5} := 150, S_{7 \times 7} := 210, S_{9 \times 9} := 270, S_{11 \times 11} := 330, S_{13 \times 13} := 390, S_{15 \times 15} := 450$ and $m := 60$.

2.7 Double-Digit Algebraic Magic Squares of Order 17

Below are three different ways of writing magic square of order 17, i.e., **cyclic**, **flat** and **cornered**.

2.7.1 Cyclic-Type

Result 2.17. Let's consider an *algebraic magic square of order 17 with reduced entries*:

a69	a70	a71	a72	a73	a74	a75	a76	a77	a78	a79	a80	a81	a82	$3^5 \cdot a76 - a74 - a75 - a73 - a72 - a71 - a70 - a69 - a82 - a81 - a80 - a79 - a78 - a77$	$2^5/5 \cdot a83$	a83		
$2^5/5 \cdot a69$	$2^5/5 \cdot a70$	$2^5/5 \cdot a71$	$2^5/5 \cdot a72$	$2^5/5 \cdot a73$	$2^5/5 \cdot a74$	$2^5/5 \cdot a75$	$2^5/5 \cdot a76$	$2^5/5 \cdot a77$	$2^5/5 \cdot a78$	$2^5/5 \cdot a79$	$2^5/5 \cdot a80$	$2^5/5 \cdot a81$	$2^5/5 \cdot a82$	$a76 + a74 + a75 + a73 + a72 + a71 + a70 + a69 + a82 + a81 + a80 + a79 + a78 + a77 - (13/5) \cdot S$	$2^5/5 \cdot a84$	a84		
$3^5 \cdot a113 - a114 + a83 - a84 - 2^5 \cdot a110 - a116 - a115 - a117 - a118 - a120 - a119 - a121 - a112 - a111 - a122$	$a113 + a114 + a84 + 2^5 \cdot a110 - a83 + a116 + a115 + a117 + a118 + a120 + a119 + a121 + a112 + a111 + a122 - (13/5) \cdot S$	a31	a32	a33	a34	a35	a36	a37	a38	a39	a40	$(11/5) \cdot S - a31 - a32 - a34 - a35 - a36 - a37 - a38 - a39 - a40 - a33$	$2^5/5 \cdot a41$	a41	$2^5/5 \cdot a85$	a85		
a122	$2^5/5 \cdot a122$	$2^5/5 \cdot a31$	$2^5/5 \cdot a32$	$2^5/5 \cdot a33$	$2^5/5 \cdot a34$	$2^5/5 \cdot a35$	$2^5/5 \cdot a36$	$2^5/5 \cdot a37$	$2^5/5 \cdot a38$	$2^5/5 \cdot a39$	$2^5/5 \cdot a40$	$a31 + a32 + a34 + a35 + a36 + a37 + a38 + a39 + a40 + a33 - (9/5) \cdot S$	$2^5/5 \cdot a42$	a42	$2^5/5 \cdot a86$	a86		
a121	$2^5/5 \cdot a121$	$(11/5) \cdot S + a41 - a42 - 2^5 \cdot a60 - a62 - a63 - a64 - a65 - a66 - a67 - a68 - a61$	$a42 + 2^5 \cdot a60 - a41 + a62 + a63 + a64 + a65 + a66 + a67 + a68 + a61 - (9/5) \cdot S$	a9	a10	a11	a12	a13	a14	$(7/5) \cdot S - a9 - a10 - a11 - a12 - a13 - a14$	$2^5/5 \cdot a15$	a15	$2^5/5 \cdot a43$	a43	$2^5/5 \cdot a87$	a87		
a120	$2^5/5 \cdot a120$	a68	$2^5/5 \cdot a68$	$2^5/5 \cdot a9$	$2^5/5 \cdot a10$	$2^5/5 \cdot a11$	$2^5/5 \cdot a12$	$2^5/5 \cdot a13$	$2^5/5 \cdot a14$	$a9 + a10 + a11 + a12 + a13 + a14 - S$	$2^5/5 \cdot a16$	a16	$2^5/5 \cdot a44$	a44	$2^5/5 \cdot a88$	a88		
a119	$2^5/5 \cdot a119$	a67	$2^5/5 \cdot a67$	$(7/5) \cdot S - a30 - a29 - a28 - a27 - 2^5 \cdot a26 + a15 - a16$	$a30 + a29 + a28 + a27 + 2^5 \cdot a26 - a15 + a16 - S$	a1	a2	$S - a1 - a2 - a3 - a4$	a3	a4	$2^5/5 \cdot a17$	a17	$2^5/5 \cdot a45$	a45	$2^5/5 \cdot a89$	a89		
a118	$2^5/5 \cdot a118$	a66	$2^5/5 \cdot a66$	a30	$2^5/5 \cdot a30$	$a8 - a2 + a7$	a5	$a1 + a2 + a3 + a4 - a5 - a6 - a7$	a6	$S - a1 - a3 - a4 - a8$	$2^5/5 \cdot a18$	a18	$2^5/5 \cdot a46$	a46	$2^5/5 \cdot a90$	a90		
a117	$2^5/5 \cdot a117$	a65	$2^5/5 \cdot a65$	a29	$2^5/5 \cdot a29$	$a2 + a3 + a4 - a5 - a7$	$S - a1 - a2 - a3 - a4 + a6 - a8$	a7	$a7 - a2 - a3 + a5 + a8$	$a1 + a2 + a3 - a6 - a7$	$2^5/5 \cdot a19$	a19	$2^5/5 \cdot a47$	a47	$2^5/5 \cdot a91$	a91		
a116	$2^5/5 \cdot a116$	a64	$2^5/5 \cdot a64$	a28	$2^5/5 \cdot a28$	$a7 - a3 + a5$	$a1 - a6 + a8$	$a2 + a3 - a7$	$S - a1 - a5 - a7 - a8$	$a7 - a2 + a6$	$2^5/5 \cdot a20$	a20	$2^5/5 \cdot a48$	a48	$2^5/5 \cdot a92$	a92		
a115	$2^5/5 \cdot a115$	a63	$2^5/5 \cdot a63$	a27	$2^5/5 \cdot a27$	$S - a1 - a4 - a7 - a8$	$a3 + a4 - a5$	$a7 - a2 - a3 + a5 + a6$	$a1 + a2 - a6$	a8	$a15 + a16 + a17 + a18 + a19 + a20 - S$	$(7/5) \cdot S - a15 - a16 - a17 - a18 - a19 - a20$	$2^5/5 \cdot a49$	a49	$2^5/5 \cdot a93$	a93		
a114	$2^5/5 \cdot a114$	a62	$2^5/5 \cdot a62$	a26	$2^5/5 \cdot a26$	$a25 + a24 + a23 + a22 + 2^5 \cdot a21 - a9 + a10 - S$	$2^5/5 \cdot a25$	$2^5/5 \cdot a24$	$2^5/5 \cdot a23$	$2^5/5 \cdot a22$	$2^5/5 \cdot a21$	$(2/5) \cdot S + a9 - a10 - a21$	$2^5/5 \cdot a50$	a50	$2^5/5 \cdot a94$	a94		
a113	$2^5/5 \cdot a113$	a61	$2^5/5 \cdot a61$	$a16 + a26 - a15$	$(2/5) \cdot S + a15 - a16 - a26$	$(7/5) \cdot S - a25 - a24 - a23 - a22 - 2^5 \cdot a21 + a9 - a10$	a25	a24	a23	a22	a21	$a10 + a21 - a9$	$a42 + a41 + a50 + a49 + a48 + a47 + a46 + a45 + a44 + a43 - (9/5) \cdot S$	$(11/5) \cdot S - a42 - a41 - a50 - a49 - a48 - a47 - a46 - a45 - a44 - a43$	$2^5/5 \cdot a95$	a95		
a112	$2^5/5 \cdot a112$	a60	$2^5/5 \cdot a60$	$a32 + 2^5 \cdot a51 - a31 + a52 + a53 + a54 + a55 + a56 + a57 + a58 + a59 - (9/5) \cdot S$	$2^5/5 \cdot a59$	$2^5/5 \cdot a58$	$2^5/5 \cdot a57$	$2^5/5 \cdot a56$	$2^5/5 \cdot a55$	$2^5/5 \cdot a54$	$2^5/5 \cdot a53$	$2^5/5 \cdot a52$	$2^5/5 \cdot a51$	$(2/5) \cdot S + a31 - a32 - a51$	$2^5/5 \cdot a96$	a96		
a111	$2^5/5 \cdot a111$	$a42 + a60 - a41$	$(2/5) \cdot S + a41 - a42 - a60$	$(11/5) \cdot S + a31 - a32 - 2^5 \cdot a51 - a52 - a53 - a54 - a55 - a56 - a57 - a58 - a59$	a59	a58	a57	a56	a55	a54	a53	a52	a51	a32 + a51 - a31	$a96 + a95 + a94 + a91 + a90 + a89 + a88 + a87 + a86 + a85 + a84 + a83 + a93 + a92 - (13/5) \cdot S$	$3^5 \cdot a96 - a95 - a94 - a91 - a90 - a89 - a88 - a87 - a86 - a85 - a84 - a83 - a93 - a92$	$2^5/5 \cdot a97$	a97
a110	$2^5/5 \cdot a110$	$a108 + a107 + a109 + a99 + a98 + 2^5 \cdot a97 + a106 + a104 + a105 + a101 + a102 + a103 + a100 - a69 + a70 - (13/5) \cdot S$	$2^5/5 \cdot a109$	$2^5/5 \cdot a108$	$2^5/5 \cdot a107$	$2^5/5 \cdot a106$	$2^5/5 \cdot a105$	$2^5/5 \cdot a104$	$2^5/5 \cdot a103$	$2^5/5 \cdot a102$	$2^5/5 \cdot a101$	$2^5/5 \cdot a100$	$2^5/5 \cdot a99$	$2^5/5 \cdot a98$	$2^5/5 \cdot a97$	$(2/5) \cdot S + a69 - a70 - a97$	a97	
$a84 + a110 - a83$	$(2/5) \cdot S + a83 - a84 - a110$	a109	a108	a107	a106	a105	a104	a103	a102	a101	a100	a99	a98	a97	a96	$a70 + a97 - a69$	a69	

• Details

It is an **algebraic cyclic-type** magic square of order 17 composed of four equal sums magic rectangles of orders 2×15 embedded with a magic square of order 13. It is again composed of four equal sums magic rectangles of order 2×11 and so on having a magic square of order 5 in the middle. In this case, the magic sums are $S_{5 \times 5} := S$, $S_{9 \times 9} := 3S$, $S_{13 \times 13} := \frac{13S}{5}$ and $S_{17 \times 17} := \frac{17S}{5}$. The width of magic rectangles is given as $m := \frac{2S}{5}$. In order to avoid decimal entries the magic sum of order 5 should be multiple of 5. Below are two examples.

Example 2.17. Let's consider following two examples based on the Result 2.17:

17	mgc	17x17	https://numbers-magic.com/	https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/	©IJT	289												
	205	208	211	214	217	220	223	226	229	232	235	238	241	244	-2888	-213	247	289
	-171	-174	-177	-180	-183	-186	-189	-192	-195	-198	-201	-204	-207	-210	2922	-216	250	289
	-4574	4608	91	94	97	100	103	106	109	112	115	118	-858	-87	121	-219	253	289
	364	-330	-57	-60	-63	-66	-69	-72	-75	-78	-81	-84	892	-90	124	-222	256	289
	361	-327	-1704	1738	25	28	31	34	37	40	-76	-9	43	-93	127	-225	259	289
	358	-324	202	-168	9	6	3	0	-3	-6	110	-12	46	-96	130	-228	262	289
	355	-321	199	-165	-370	404	1	4	63	7	10	-15	49	-99	133	-231	265	289
	352	-318	196	-162	88	-54	37	13	-26	16	45	-18	52	-102	136	-234	268	289
	349	-315	193	-159	85	-51	-11	57	19	43	-23	-21	55	-105	139	-237	271	289
	346	-312	190	-156	82	-48	25	7	-8	30	31	-24	58	-108	142	-240	274	289
	343	-309	187	-153	79	-45	33	4	37	-11	22	218	-184	-111	145	-243	277	289
	340	-306	184	-150	76	-42	314	-39	-36	-33	-30	-27	-30	-114	148	-246	280	289
	337	-303	181	-147	79	-45	-280	73	70	67	64	61	64	1192	-1158	-249	283	289
	334	-300	178	-144	1468	-141	-138	-135	-132	-129	-126	-123	-120	-117	-120	-252	286	289
	331	-297	181	-147	-1434	175	172	169	166	163	160	157	154	151	154	3510	-3476	289
	328	-294	4062	-291	-288	-285	-282	-279	-276	-273	-270	-267	-264	-261	-258	-255	-258	289
	331	-297	-4028	325	322	319	316	313	310	307	304	301	298	295	292	289	292	289
	289	289	289	289	289	289	289	289	289	289	289	289	289	289	289	289	289	289

17	mgc	17x17	https://numbers-magic.com/	https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/	©IJT	357												
	205	208	211	214	217	220	223	226	229	232	235	238	241	244	-2828	-205	247	357
	-163	-166	-169	-172	-175	-178	-181	-184	-187	-190	-193	-196	-199	-202	2870	-208	250	357
	-4514	4556	91	94	97	100	103	106	109	112	115	118	-814	-79	121	-211	253	357
	364	-322	-49	-52	-55	-58	-61	-64	-67	-70	-73	-76	856	-82	124	-214	256	357
	361	-319	-1660	1702	25	28	31	34	37	40	-48	-1	43	-85	127	-217	259	357
	358	-316	202	-160	17	14	11	8	5	2	90	-4	46	-88	130	-220	262	357
	355	-313	199	-157	-342	384	1	4	83	7	10	-7	49	-91	133	-223	265	357
	352	-310	196	-154	88	-46	37	13	-26	16	65	-10	52	-94	136	-226	268	357
	349	-307	193	-151	85	-43	-11	77	19	43	-23	-13	55	-97	139	-229	271	357
	346	-304	190	-148	82	-40	25	7	-8	50	31	-16	58	-100	142	-232	274	357
	343	-301	187	-145	79	-37	53	4	37	-11	22	198	-156	-103	145	-235	277	357
	340	-298	184	-142	76	-34	294	-31	-28	-25	-22	-19	-22	-106	148	-238	280	357
	337	-295	181	-139	79	-37	-252	73	70	67	64	61	64	1156	-1114	-241	283	357
	334	-292	178	-136	1432	-133	-130	-127	-124	-121	-118	-115	-112	-109	-112	-244	286	357
	331	-289	181	-139	-1390	175	172	169	166	163	160	157	154	151	154	3458	-3416	357
	328	-286	4010	-283	-280	-277	-274	-271	-268	-265	-262	-259	-256	-253	-250	-247	-250	357
	331	-289	-3968	325	322	319	316	313	310	307	304	301	298	295	292	289	292	357
	357	357	357	357	357	357	357	357	357	357	357	357	357	357	357	357	357	357

The magic sums are:

- *First example:* $S_{5 \times 5} := 85, S_{9 \times 9} := 153, S_{13 \times 13} := 221, S_{17 \times 17} := 289$ and $m := 34$.
- *Second example:* $S_{5 \times 5} := 105, S_{9 \times 9} := 189, S_{13 \times 13} := 273, S_{17 \times 17} := 357$ and $m := 42$.

2.7.2 Flat-Type

Result 2.18. *Let's consider an algebraic magic square of order 17 with reduced entries:*

a69	a70	a71	a72	a73	a74	a75	a76	a77	a78	a79	a80	a81	a82	(17/5)*S-a78-a79-a72-a73-a84-a74-a81-a69-a75-a76-a77-a71-a83-a82-a80-a70	a83	a84		
2*S/5-a69	2*S/5-a70	2*S/5-a71	2*S/5-a72	2*S/5-a73	2*S/5-a74	2*S/5-a75	2*S/5-a76	2*S/5-a77	2*S/5-a78	2*S/5-a79	2*S/5-a80	2*S/5-a81	2*S/5-a82	a78+a79+a72+a73+a84+a74+a81+a69+a75+a76+a77+a71+a83+a82-a80-a70-3*S	2*S/5-a83	2*S/5-a84		
(13/5)*S-a122-a121-a120-a119-a118-a117-a116-a115-a114-a113-a112-a111	a122+a121+a120+a119+a118+a117+a116+a115+a114+a113+a112+a111-(11/5)*S	a31	a32	a33	a34	a35	a36	a37	a38	a39	a40	(13/5)*S-a34-a33-a41-a42-a35-a36-a37-a32-a31-a38-a40-a39	a41	a42	2*S/5-a85	a85		
a122	2*S/5-a122	2*S/5-a31	2*S/5-a32	2*S/5-a33	2*S/5-a34	2*S/5-a35	2*S/5-a36	2*S/5-a37	2*S/5-a38	2*S/5-a39	2*S/5-a40	a34+a33+a41+a42+a35+a36+a37+a32+a31+a38+a40+a39-(11/5)*S	2*S/5-a41	2*S/5-a42	2*S/5-a86	a86		
a121	2*S/5-a121	(9/5)*S-a68-a67-a66-a65-a64-a63-a62-a61	a68+a67+a66+a65+a64+a63+a62+a61-(7/5)*S	a9	a10	a11	a12	a13	a14	(9/5)*S-a9-a10-a11-a12-a13-a14-a15-a16	a15	a16	2*S/5-a43	a43	2*S/5-a87	a87		
a120	2*S/5-a120	a68	2*S/5-a68	2*S/5-a9	2*S/5-a10	2*S/5-a11	2*S/5-a12	2*S/5-a13	2*S/5-a14	a9+a10+a11+a12+a13+a14+a15+a16-(7/5)*S	2*S/5-a15	2*S/5-a16	2*S/5-a44	a44	2*S/5-a88	a88		
a119	2*S/5-a119	a67	2*S/5-a67	S-a27-a28-a29-a30	a27+a28+a29+a30-(3/5)*S	a1	a2	S-a1-a2-a3-a4	a3	a4	2*S/5-a23	a23	2*S/5-a45	a45	2*S/5-a89	a89		
a118	2*S/5-a118	a66	2*S/5-a66	a27	2*S/5-a27	a8-a2+a7	a5	a1+a2+a3+a4-a5-a6-a7	a6	S-a1-a3-a4-a8	2*S/5-a24	a24	2*S/5-a46	a46	2*S/5-a90	a90		
a117	2*S/5-a117	a65	2*S/5-a65	a28	2*S/5-a28	a2+a3+a4-a5-a7	S-a1-a2-a3-a4+a6-a8	a7	a7-a2-a3+a5+a8	a1+a2+a3-a6-a7	2*S/5-a25	a25	2*S/5-a47	a47	2*S/5-a91	a91		
a116	2*S/5-a116	a64	2*S/5-a64	a29	2*S/5-a29	a7-a3+a5	a1-a6+a8	a2+a3-a7	S-a1-a5-a7-a8	a7-a2+a6	2*S/5-a26	a26	2*S/5-a48	a48	2*S/5-a92	a92		
a115	2*S/5-a115	a63	2*S/5-a63	a30	2*S/5-a30	S-a1-a4-a7-a8	a3+a4-a5	a7-a2-a3+a5+a6	a1+a2-a6	a8	a23+a24+a25+a26-(3/5)*S	S-a23-a24-a25-a26	2*S/5-a49	a49	2*S/5-a93	a93		
a114	2*S/5-a114	a62	2*S/5-a62	(2/5)*S+a16-a15-a17	2*S/5-a17	a15+2*a17+a18+a19+a20+a21+2*a22-a9+a10-(7/5)*S-a16	2*S/5-a18	2*S/5-a19	2*S/5-a20	2*S/5-a21	2*S/5-a22	(2/5)*S+a9-a10-a22	2*S/5-a50	a50	2*S/5-a94	a94		
a113	2*S/5-a113	a61	2*S/5-a61	a15+a17-a16	a17	(9/5)*S+a16-a15-2*a17-a18-a19-a20-a21-2*a22+a9-a10	a18	a19	a20	a21	a22	a10+a22-a9	a43+a44+a45+a46+a47+a48+a49+a50-(7/5)*S	(9/5)*S-a43-a44-a45-a46-a47-a48-a49-a50	2*S/5-a95	a95		
a112	2*S/5-a112	(2/5)*S+a42-a41-a60	2*S/5-a60	a41-a42+2*a60+a32-a31+2*a51+a52+a53+a54+a55+a56+a57+a58+a59-(11/5)*S	2*S/5-a59	2*S/5-a58	2*S/5-a57	2*S/5-a56	2*S/5-a55	2*S/5-a54	2*S/5-a53	2*S/5-a52	2*S/5-a51	(2/5)*S+a31-a32-a51	2*S/5-a96	a96		
a111	2*S/5-a111	a41+a60-a42	a60	(13/5)*S-a41+a42-2*a60-a32+a31-2*a51-a52-a53-a54-a55-a56-a57-a58-a59	a59	a58	a57	a56	a55	a54	a53	a52	a51	a32+a51-a31	a96+a95+a85+a86+a87+a88+a89+a90+a94+a93+a91+a92-(11/5)*S	(13/5)*S-a96-a95-a86-a87-a88-a89-a90-a94-a93-a91-a92	2*S/5-a97	a97
(2/5)*S+a84-a83-a110	2*S/5-a110	a103+a102+a105+a104+a106+a101+a100-a69+a108+a107+a109+a98+a99+2*a110+a83+2*a97+a70-3*S-a84	2*S/5-a109	2*S/5-a108	2*S/5-a107	2*S/5-a106	2*S/5-a105	2*S/5-a104	2*S/5-a103	2*S/5-a102	2*S/5-a101	2*S/5-a100	2*S/5-a99	2*S/5-a98	2*S/5-a97	(2/5)*S+a69-a70-a97	2*S/5-a98	
a83+a110-a84	a110	(17/5)*S+a84-a103-a102-a105-a104-a106-a101-a100+a69-a108-a107-a109-a98-a99-2*a110-a83-2*a97-a70	a109	a108	a107	a106	a105	a104	a103	a102	a101	a100	a99	a98	a97	a70+a97-a69	2*S/5-a97	

• Details

It is an **algebraic flat-type** magic square of order 15 composed of two equal sums magic rectangles of orders 2×15 and two equal sums magic rectangles of order 2×11 embedded again with a **flat-type** magic square of order 11 and so on. In this case, the magic sums are $S_{5 \times 5} := S$, $S_{9 \times 9} := 3S$, $S_{13 \times 13} := \frac{13S}{5}$ and $S_{17 \times 17} := \frac{17S}{5}$. The width of magic rectangles is given as $m := \frac{2S}{5}$. In order to avoid decimal entries the magic sum of order 5 should be multiple of 5. Below are two examples.

Example 2.18. Let's consider following two examples based on the Result 2.18:

17	mgc	17x17	https://numbers-magic.com/	https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/	©IJT	323	
		70 71 72 73 74 75 76 77 78 79 80 81 82 83 -917 84 85				323	
		-32 -33 -34 -35 -36 -37 -38 -39 -40 -41 -42 -43 -44 -45 955 -46 -47				323	
		-1163 1201	32 33 34 35 36 37 38 39 40 41 -203 42 43		-48 86	323	
		123 -85	6 5 4 3 2 1 0 -1 -2 -3 241 -4 -5		-49 87	323	
		122 -84	-353 391	10 11 12 13 14 15 63 16 17	-6 44	323	
		121 -83	69 -31	28 27 26 25 24 23 -25 22 21	-7 45	323	
		120 -82	68 -30	-23 61	2 3 81 4 5	14 24	323
		119 -81	67 -29	28 10	14 6 -7 7 75	13 25	323
		118 -80	66 -28	29 9	-2 79 8 16 -6	12 26	323
		117 -79	65 -27	30 8	10 4 -1 70 12	11 27	323
		116 -78	64 -26	31 7	71 3 14 -2 9	45 -7	323
		115 -77	63 -25	21 20	31 19 18 17 16 15 14	-13 51	323
		114 -76	62 -24	17 18 7 19 20 21 22 23 24	247 -209	-58 96	323
		113 -75	-22 -23 469 -22 -21 -20 -19 -18 -17 -16 -15 -14 -15		-59 97	323	
		112 -74	60 61 -431 60 59 58 57 56 55 54 53 52 53		889 -851	323	
		-72 -73 1387 -72 -71 -70 -69 -68 -67 -66 -65 -64 -63 -62 -61 -60 -61				323	
		110 111 -1349 110 109 108 107 106 105 104 103 102 101 100 99 98 99				323	
		323 323 323 323 323 323 323 323 323 323 323 323 323 323 323 323 323				323	

17	mgc	17x17	https://numbers-magic.com/	https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/	©IJT	425	
		70 71 72 73 74 75 76 77 78 79 80 81 82 83 -815 84 85				425	
		-20 -21 -22 -23 -24 -25 -26 -27 -28 -29 -30 -31 -32 -33 865 -34 -35				425	
		-1085 1135	32 33 34 35 36 37 38 39 40 41 -125 42 43		-36 86	425	
		123 -73	18 17 16 15 14 13 12 11 10 9 175 8 7		-37 87	425	
		122 -72	-299 349	10 11 12 13 14 15 117 16 17	6 44	425	
		121 -71	69 -19	40 39 38 37 36 35 -67 34 33	5 45	425	
		120 -70	68 -18	7 43	2 3 111 4 5	26 24	425
		119 -69	67 -17	28 22	14 6 -7 7 105	25 25	425
		118 -68	66 -16	29 21	-2 109 8 16 -6	24 26	425
		117 -67	65 -15	30 20	10 4 -1 100 12	23 27	425
		116 -66	64 -14	31 19	101 3 14 -2 9	27 23	425
		115 -65	63 -13	33 32 -11 31 30 29 28 27 26	-1 51	-45 95	425
		114 -64	62 -12	17 18 61 19 20 21 22 23 24	205 -155	-46 96	425
		113 -63	-10 -11 403 -10 -9 -8 -7 -6 -5 -4 -3 -2 -3		-47 97	425	
		112 -62	60 61 -353 60 59 58 57 56 55 54 53 52 53		823 -773	425	
		-60 -61 1297 -60 -59 -58 -57 -56 -55 -54 -53 -52 -51 -50 -49 -48 -49				425	
		110 111 -1247 110 109 108 107 106 105 104 103 102 101 100 99 98 99				425	
		425 425 425 425 425 425 425 425 425 425 425 425 425 425 425 425 425				425	

The magic sums are:

- **First example:** $S_{5 \times 5} := 95, S_{9 \times 9} := 171, S_{13 \times 13} := 247, S_{17 \times 17} := 323$ and $m := 38$.
- **Second example:** $S_{5 \times 5} := 125, S_{9 \times 9} := 225, S_{13 \times 13} := 325, S_{17 \times 17} := 425$ and $m := 50$.

2.7.3 Cornered

Result 2.19. *Let's consider an algebraic magic square of order 17 with reduced entries:*

$a1+a2-S/3$	$2^*S/3-a2$	$2^*S/3-a1$	$2^*S/3-a3$	$a3$	$2^*S/3-a7$	$a7$	$2^*S/3-a15$	$a15$	$2^*S/3-a27$	$a27$	$2^*S/3-a43$	$a43$	$2^*S/3-a63$	$a63$	$2^*S/3-a87$	$a87$	
$4^*S/3-2^*a1-a2$	$S/3$	$2^*a1+a2-2^*S/3$	$2^*S/3-a4$	$a4$	$2^*S/3-a8$	$a8$	$2^*S/3-a16$	$a16$	$2^*S/3-a28$	$a28$	$2^*S/3-a44$	$a44$	$2^*S/3-a64$	$a64$	$2^*S/3-a88$	$a88$	
$a1$	$a2$	$S-a1-a2$	$a3+a4-(1/3)^*S$	$S-a3-a4$	$2^*S/3-a9$	$a9$	$2^*S/3-a17$	$a17$	$2^*S/3-a29$	$a29$	$2^*S/3-a45$	$a45$	$2^*S/3-a65$	$a65$	$2^*S/3-a89$	$a89$	
$(4/3)^*S+a3-a4-a1-a2-a5$	$2^*S/3-a5$	$a4+a1+a2+2^*a5+2^*a6-(5/3)^*S-a3$	$2^*S/3-a6$	$2^*S/3-a6$	$2^*S/3-a10$	$a10$	$2^*S/3-a18$	$a18$	$2^*S/3-a30$	$a30$	$2^*S/3-a46$	$a46$	$2^*S/3-a66$	$a66$	$2^*S/3-a90$	$a90$	
$a4+a1+a2+a5-(2/3)^*S-a3$	$a5$	$(7/3)^*S+a3-a4-a1-a2-2^*a5-2^*a6$	$a6$	$a6$	$a7+a8+a9+a10-S$	$(5/3)^*S-a7-a8-a9-a10$	$2^*S/3-a19$	$a19$	$2^*S/3-a31$	$a31$	$2^*S/3-a47$	$a47$	$2^*S/3-a67$	$a67$	$2^*S/3-a91$	$a91$	
$(11/3)^*S+a7-a8-2^*a4-3^*a6-a1-a2-2^*a5-a11$	$2^*S/3-a11$	$2^*S/3-a12$	$2^*S/3-a13$	$a8+2^*a4+3^*a6+a1+a2+2^*a5+2^*a11+a12+a13+2^*a14-(14/3)^*S-a7$	$2^*S/3-a14$	$2^*S/3-a14$	$2^*S/3-a20$	$a20$	$2^*S/3-a32$	$a32$	$2^*S/3-a48$	$a48$	$2^*S/3-a68$	$a68$	$2^*S/3-a92$	$a92$	
$a8+2^*a4+3^*a6+a1+a2+2^*a5+a11-3^*S-a7$	$a11$	$a12$	$a13$	$(16/3)^*S+a7-a8-2^*a4-3^*a6-a1-a2-2^*a5-2^*a11-a12-a13-2^*a14$	$a14$	$a14$	$a15+a16+a17+a18+a19+a20-(5/3)^*S$	$(7/3)^*S-a15-a16-a17-a18-a19-a20$	$2^*S/3-a33$	$a33$	$2^*S/3-a49$	$a49$	$2^*S/3-a69$	$a69$	$2^*S/3-a93$	$a93$	
$S+a15-a16+a9-a10+a6-a13+a12-a21$	$2^*S/3-a21$	$2^*S/3-a22$	$2^*S/3-a23$	$2^*S/3-a24$	$2^*S/3-a25$	$a16-a9+a10-a6+a13-a12+2^*a21+a22+a23+a24+a25+2^*a26-(8/3)^*S-a15$	$2^*S/3-a26$	$2^*S/3-a26$	$2^*S/3-a34$	$a34$	$2^*S/3-a50$	$a50$	$2^*S/3-a70$	$a70$	$2^*S/3-a94$	$a94$	
$a16-a9+a10-a6+a13-a12+a21-(1/3)^*S-a15$	$a21$	$a22$	$a23$	$a24$	$a25$	$(10/3)^*S+a15-a16+a9-a10+a6-a13+a12-2^*a21-a22-a23-a24-a25-2^*a26$	$a26$	$a26$	$a27+a28+a29+a30+a31+a32+a33+a34-(7/3)^*S$	$3^*S-a27-a28-a29-a30-a31-a32-a33-a34$	$2^*S/3-a51$	$a51$	$2^*S/3-a71$	$a71$	$2^*S/3-a95$	$a95$	
$(22/3)^*S+a22-3^*a14-a35-2^*a11-a10-a17-a13-a9-a18-a12-a1-a2-a23-2^*a8-a28-3^*a6+a27-2^*a5-2^*a4$	$2^*S/3-a35$	$2^*S/3-a36$	$2^*S/3-a37$	$2^*S/3-a38$	$2^*S/3-a39$	$2^*S/3-a40$	$2^*S/3-a41$	$3^*a14+a41+2^*a42+2^*a35+a36+2^*a11+a10-a17+a13+a9+a37+a18+a12+a1+a2+a38+a23+2^*a8+a40+a28+3^*a6-a27+2^*a5+2^*a4-(29/3)^*S+a39-a22$	$2^*S/3-a42$	$2^*S/3-a42$	$2^*S/3-a52$	$a52$	$2^*S/3-a72$	$a72$	$2^*S/3-a96$	$a96$	
$3^*a14+a35+2^*a11+a10-a17+a13+a9+a18+a12+a1+a2+a23+2^*a8+a28+3^*a6-a27+2^*a5+2^*a4-(20/3)^*S-a22$	$a35$	$a36$	$a37$	$a38$	$a39$	$a40$	$a41$	$a42$	$a42$	$a42$	$a43+a44+a45+a46+a47+a48+a49+a50+a51+a52-3^*S$	$(11/3)^*S-a43-a44-a45-a46-a47-a48-a49-a50-a51-a52$	$2^*S/3-a73$	$a73$	$2^*S/3-a97$	$a97$	
$(1/3)^*S+a43-a44+a29-a30+a19-a20+a14-a25+a24-a37+a36-a53$	$2^*S/3-a53$	$2^*S/3-a54$	$2^*S/3-a55$	$2^*S/3-a56$	$2^*S/3-a57$	$2^*S/3-a58$	$2^*S/3-a59$	$2^*S/3-a60$	$2^*S/3-a61$	$2^*S/3-a61$	$a44+2^*a62+a61+a60+a59+a58+a57+a56+a55+a54+2^*a53-a36+a37+a20-a14-a19+a30-a29+a25-a24-(10/3)^*S-a43$	$2^*S/3-a62$	$2^*S/3-a62$	$2^*S/3-a74$	$a74$	$2^*S/3-a98$	$a98$
$(1/3)^*S-a43+a44-a29+a30-a19-a20-a14+a25-a24+a37-a36+a53$	$a53$	$a54$	$a55$	$a56$	$a57$	$a58$	$a59$	$a60$	$a61$	$a61$	$4^*S+a43-a44-2^*a62-a61-a60-a59-a58-a57-a56-a55-a54-2^*a53+a36-a37-a20-a14+a19-a30+a29-a25-a24-(11/3)^*S$	$a62$	$a62$	$a63+a64+a65+a66+a67+a68+a69+a70+a71+a72+a73+a74-(11/3)^*S$	$(13/3)^*S-a63-a64-a65-a66-a67-a68-a69-a70-a71-a72-a73-a74$	$2^*S/3-a99$	$a99$
$6^*S-a75-a55+a54+a38-a39-a23-a24-a25-a12-2^*a21-a22+a9-a10-a13-3^*a26-a20-2^*a16-a17-a18-a19-a32+a31+a45-a46+a6-a64+a63$	$2^*S/3-a75$	$2^*S/3-a76$	$2^*S/3-a77$	$2^*S/3-a78$	$2^*S/3-a79$	$2^*S/3-a80$	$2^*S/3-a81$	$2^*S/3-a82$	$2^*S/3-a83$	$2^*S/3-a84$	$2^*S/3-a85$	$a82+a81+a80+a79+a78+a77+a76-(29/3)^*S+2^*a75+a55-a54-a38+a39+a23+a24+a25-a12+2^*a21+a22-a9-a10-a13-3^*a26-a20+2^*a16+a17+a18+a19-a32-a31-a45+a46-a6+2^*a86+a85+a84+a83+a64-a63$	$2^*S/3-a86$	$2^*S/3-a86$	$2^*S/3-a100$	$a100$	
$a75+a55-a54-a38+a39+a23+a24+a25-a12+2^*a21+a22-a9+a10-a13-3^*a26-a20+2^*a16+a17+a18+a19-a32+a31+a45-a46+a6-a64-a63-(16/3)^*S$	$a75$	$a76$	$a77$	$a78$	$a79$	$a80$	$a81$	$a82$	$a83$	$a84$	$a85$	$(31/3)^*S-2^*a75-a55+a54+a38-a39-a23-a24-a25-a12-2^*a21-a22+a9-a10-a13-3^*a26-a20-2^*a16-a17-a18-a19-a32+a31+a45-a46+a6-2^*a86-a85-a84-a83-a64+a63-a82-a81-a80-a79-a78-a77-a76$	$a86$	$a86$	$a87+a88+a89+a90+a91+a92+a93+a94+a95+a96+a97+a98+a99+a100-(13/3)^*S$	$5^*S-a87-a88-a89-a90-a91-a92-a93-a94-a95-a96-a97-a98-a99-a100$	
$(1/3)^*S-a77+a76-a88+a87-a57-a56+a40-a41-a34-a48+a33+a47+a26-a101-a66+a65$	$2^*S/3-a101$	$2^*S/3-a102$	$2^*S/3-a103$	$2^*S/3-a104$	$2^*S/3-a105$	$2^*S/3-a106$	$2^*S/3-a107$	$2^*S/3-a108$	$2^*S/3-a109$	$2^*S/3-a110$	$2^*S/3-a111$	$2^*S/3-a112$	$2^*S/3-a113$	$a77+a111+a112+a113-a76+a88+2^*a114+a107+a108-a87+a57-a56-a40+a41+a34+a48-a33-a47-a26+a109+a110+2^*a101+a102-(14/3)^*S+a66-a65+a105+a106+a103+a104$	$2^*S/3-a114$	$2^*S/3-a114$	
$(1/3)^*S+a77-a76+a88-a87+a57-a56-a40+a41+a34+a48-a33-a47-a26+a101+a66-a65$	$a101$	$a102$	$a103$	$a104$	$a105$	$a106$	$a107$	$a108$	$a109$	$a110$	$a111$	$a112$	$a113$	$a76-a88-2^*a114-a107-a108+a87-a57+a56+a40-a41-a34-a48+a33+a47+a26-a109-a110-2^*a101-a102+(16/3)^*S-a66-a65-a105-a106-a103-a104-a77-a111-a112-a113$	$a114$	$a114$	

• Details

It is an algebraic cornered, where the magic squares of orders 17, where the magic squares of order 3, 5, 7, 9, 11, 13 and 15 are at the upper-left corner. In this case, the magic sums are $S_{3 \times 3} := S, S_{5 \times 5} := \frac{5S}{3}, S_{7 \times 7} := \frac{7S}{3}, S_{9 \times 9} := 3S, S_{11 \times 11} := \frac{11S}{3}, S_{13 \times 13} := \frac{13S}{3}, S_{15 \times 15} := 5S$ and $S_{17 \times 17} := \frac{17S}{3}$. The width of magic rectangles is given as $m := \frac{2S}{3}$. In order to avoid decimal entries the magic sum of order 3 should be multiple of 3. Below are two examples.

Example 2.19. Let's consider following two examples based on the Result 2.19:

17	mgc	17x17															561	
		https://numbers-magic.com/							https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/							©IJT		
	-30	64	65	63	3	59	7	51	15	39	27	23	43	3	63	-21	87	561
	128	33	-62	62	4	58	8	50	16	38	28	22	44	2	64	-22	88	561
	1	2	96	-26	92	57	9	49	17	37	29	21	45	1	65	-23	89	561
	123	61	-139	60	60	56	10	48	18	36	30	20	46	0	66	-24	90	561
	-57	5	205	6	6	-65	131	47	19	35	31	19	47	-1	67	-25	91	561
	312	55	54	53	-347	52	52	46	20	34	32	18	48	-2	68	-26	92	561
	-246	11	12	13	413	14	14	-60	126	33	33	17	49	-3	69	-27	93	561
	81	45	44	43	42	41	-79	40	40	32	34	16	50	-4	70	-28	94	561
	-15	21	22	23	24	25	145	26	26	13	53	15	51	-5	71	-29	95	561
	525	31	30	29	28	27	26	25	-406	24	24	14	52	-6	72	-30	96	561
	-459	35	36	37	38	39	40	41	472	42	42	178	-112	-7	73	-31	97	561
	-11	13	12	11	10	9	8	7	6	5	351	4	4	-8	74	-32	98	561
	77	53	54	55	56	57	58	59	60	61	-285	62	62	459	-393	-33	99	561
	198	-9	-10	-11	-12	-13	-14	-15	-16	-17	-18	-19	491	-20	-20	-34	100	561
	-132	75	76	77	78	79	80	81	82	83	84	85	-425	86	86	880	-814	561
	-49	-35	-36	-37	-38	-39	-40	-41	-42	-43	-44	-45	-46	-47	1239	-48	-48	561
	115	101	102	103	104	105	106	107	108	109	110	111	112	113	-1173	114	114	561
	561	561	561	561	561	561	561	561	561	561	561	561	561	561	561	561	561	561

17	mgc	17x17															663	
		https://numbers-magic.com/							https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/							©IJT		
	-36	76	77	75	3	71	7	63	15	51	27	35	43	15	63	-9	87	663
	152	39	-74	74	4	70	8	62	16	50	28	34	44	14	64	-10	88	663
	1	2	114	-32	110	69	9	61	17	49	29	33	45	13	65	-11	89	663
	147	73	-169	72	72	68	10	60	18	48	30	32	46	12	66	-12	90	663
	-69	5	247	6	6	-83	161	59	19	47	31	31	47	11	67	-13	91	663
	378	67	66	65	-431	64	64	58	20	46	32	30	48	10	68	-14	92	663
	-300	11	12	13	509	14	14	-90	168	45	33	29	49	9	69	-15	93	663
	99	57	56	55	54	53	-127	52	52	44	34	28	50	8	70	-16	94	663
	-21	21	22	23	24	25	205	26	26	-29	107	27	51	7	71	-17	95	663
	657	43	42	41	40	39	38	37	-580	36	36	26	52	6	72	-18	96	663
	-579	35	36	37	38	39	40	41	658	42	42	124	-46	5	73	-19	97	663
	-5	25	24	23	22	21	20	19	18	17	291	16	16	4	74	-20	98	663
	83	53	54	55	56	57	58	59	60	61	-213	62	62	393	-315	-21	99	663
	306	3	2	1	0	-1	-2	-3	-4	-5	-6	-7	317	-8	-8	-22	100	663
	-228	75	76	77	78	79	80	81	82	83	84	85	-239	86	86	802	-724	663
	-43	-23	-24	-25	-26	-27	-28	-29	-30	-31	-32	-33	-34	-35	1155	-36	-36	663
	121	101	102	103	104	105	106	107	108	109	110	111	112	113	-1077	114	114	663
	663	663	663	663	663	663	663	663	663	663	663	663	663	663	663	663	663	663

The magic sums are:

- **First example:** $S_{3 \times 3} := 99, S_{5 \times 5} := 165, S_{7 \times 7} := 231, S_{9 \times 9} := 297, S_{11 \times 11} := 363, S_{13 \times 13} := 429, S_{15 \times 15} := 495, S_{17 \times 17} := 561$ and $m := 66$.
- **Second example:** $S_{3 \times 3} := 117, S_{5 \times 5} := 195, S_{7 \times 7} := 273, S_{9 \times 9} := 351, S_{11 \times 11} := 429, S_{13 \times 13} := 507, S_{15 \times 15} := 585, S_{17 \times 17} := 663$ and $m := 78$.

2.8 Double-Digit Algebraic Magic Squares of Order 19

Below are three different ways of writing magic square of order 19, i.e., **cyclic**, **flat** and **cornered**.

2.8.1 Cyclic-Type

Result 2.20. *Let's consider an algebraic magic square of order 19 with reduced entries:*

a94	a95	a96	a97	a98	a99	a100	a101	a102	a103	a104	a105	a106	a107	a108	a109	(17/3)*S-a108-a107-a109-a99-a98-a97-a96-a95-a106-a104-a105-a101-a102-a103-a100-a94	2*S/3-a110	a110		
2*S/3-a94	2*S/3-a95	2*S/3-a96	2*S/3-a97	2*S/3-a98	2*S/3-a99	2*S/3-a100	2*S/3-a101	2*S/3-a102	2*S/3-a103	2*S/3-a104	2*S/3-a105	2*S/3-a106	2*S/3-a107	2*S/3-a108	2*S/3-a109	a108+a107+a109+a99+a98+a97+a96+a95+a106+a104+a105+a101+a102+a103+a100+a94-5*S	2*S/3-a111	a111		
(17/3)*S-a145-a144-a143-a149-a148-a147-a146+a110-a111-2*a141-a152-a151-a150-a155-a154-a153-a142	a145+a144+a143+a149+a148+a147-a146+a110-a111-2*a141-a152-a151-a150-a155-a154-a153-a142	a48	a49	a50	a51	a52	a53	a54	a55	a56	a57	a58	a59	(13/3)*S-a59-a58-a57-a56-a55-a54-a53-a52-a51-a50-a49-a48	2*S/3-a60	a60	2*S/3-a112	a112		
a155	2*S/3-a155	2*S/3-a48	2*S/3-a49	2*S/3-a50	2*S/3-a51	2*S/3-a52	2*S/3-a53	2*S/3-a54	2*S/3-a55	2*S/3-a56	2*S/3-a57	2*S/3-a58	2*S/3-a59	a59+a58+a57+a56+a55+a54+a53+a52+a51+a50+a49+a48-(11/3)*S	2*S/3-a61	a61	2*S/3-a113	a113		
a154	2*S/3-a154	(13/3)*S-a92-a93-a89-a90-a91-a88-a84-a85-a86-2*a83+a60-a87-a61	a92+a93+a89+a90+a91+a88+a84+a85+a86+2*a83-a60+a87+a61-(11/3)*S	a17	a18	a19	a20	a21	a22	a23	a24	3*S-a17-a18-a19-a20-a21-a22-a23-a24	2*S/3-a25	a25	2*S/3-a62	a62	2*S/3-a114	a114		
a153	2*S/3-a153	a93	2*S/3-a93	2*S/3-a17	2*S/3-a18	2*S/3-a19	2*S/3-a20	2*S/3-a21	2*S/3-a22	2*S/3-a23	2*S/3-a24	a17+a18+a19+a20+a21+a22+a23+a24-(7/3)*S	2*S/3-a26	a26	2*S/3-a63	a63	2*S/3-a115	a115		
a152	2*S/3-a152	a92	2*S/3-a92	3*S-a47-a46-a45-a44-a43-a42-2*a41+a25-a26	a47+a46+a45+a44+a43+a42+2*a41-a25+a26-(7/3)*S	a3	a4	a5	a6	(5/3)*S-a3-a4-a5-a6	2*S/3-a7	a7	2*S/3-a27	a27	2*S/3-a64	a64	2*S/3-a116	a116		
a151	2*S/3-a151	a91	2*S/3-a91	a47	2*S/3-a47	2*S/3-a3	2*S/3-a4	2*S/3-a5	2*S/3-a6	a3+a4+a5+a6-5	2*S/3-a8	a8	2*S/3-a28	a28	2*S/3-a65	a65	2*S/3-a117	a117		
a150	2*S/3-a150	a90	2*S/3-a90	a46	2*S/3-a46	(5/3)*S+a7-a8-2*a14-a15-a16	a8+2*a14+a15+a16-5-a7	a1+a2-5/3	2*S/3-a2	2*S/3-a1	2*S/3-a9	a9	2*S/3-a29	a29	2*S/3-a66	a66	2*S/3-a118	a118		
a149	2*S/3-a149	a89	2*S/3-a89	a45	2*S/3-a45	a16	2*S/3-a16	4*S/3-2*a1-a2	5/3	2*a1+a2-2*S/3	2*S/3-a10	a10	2*S/3-a30	a30	2*S/3-a67	a67	2*S/3-a119	a119		
a148	2*S/3-a148	a88	2*S/3-a88	a44	2*S/3-a44	a15	2*S/3-a15	a1	a2	5-a1-a2	a7+a8+a9+a10-5	(5/3)*S-a7-a8-a9-a10	2*S/3-a31	a31	2*S/3-a68	a68	2*S/3-a120	a120		
a147	2*S/3-a147	a87	2*S/3-a87	a43	2*S/3-a43	a14	2*S/3-a14	a4+2*a11+a12+a13-5-a3	2*S/3-a13	2*S/3-a12	2*S/3-a11	2*S/3+a3-a4-a11	2*S/3-a32	a32	2*S/3-a69	a69	2*S/3-a121	a121		
a146	2*S/3-a146	a86	2*S/3-a86	a42	2*S/3-a42	a8+a14-a7	2*S/3+a7-a8-a14	(5/3)*S+a3-a4-2*a11-a12-a13	a13	a12	a11	a4+a11-a3	a25+a26+a27+a28+a29+a30+a31+a32-(7/3)*S	3*S-a25-a26-a27-a28-a29-a30-a31-a32	2*S/3-a70	a70	2*S/3-a122	a122		
a145	2*S/3-a145	a85	2*S/3-a85	a41	2*S/3-a41	a39+a38+a37+a36+a35+a34+2*a33-a17+a18-(7/3)*S	2*S/3-a39	2*S/3-a38	2*S/3-a37	2*S/3-a36	2*S/3-a35	2*S/3-a34	2*S/3-a33	2*S/3+a17-a18-a33	2*S/3-a71	a71	2*S/3-a123	a123		
a144	2*S/3-a144	a84	2*S/3-a84	a26+a41-a25	2*S/3+a25-a26-a41	3*S-a39-a38-a37-a36-a35-a34-2*a33+a17-a18	a39	a38	a37	a36	a35	a34	a33	a18+a33-a17	a71+a70+a69+a68+a67+a60+a66+a65+a64+a63+a62+a61-(11/3)*S	(13/3)*S-a71-a70-a69-a68-a67-a60-a66-a65-a64-a63-a62-a61	2*S/3-a124	a124		
a143	2*S/3-a143	a83	2*S/3-a83	2*a72+a73+a74+a75+a76+a77+a78+a79+a80+a81+a82-a48+a49-(11/3)*S	2*S/3-a82	2*S/3-a81	2*S/3-a80	2*S/3-a79	2*S/3-a78	2*S/3-a77	2*S/3-a76	2*S/3-a75	2*S/3-a74	2*S/3-a73	2*S/3-a72	2*S/3+a48-a49-a72	2*S/3-a125	a125		
a142	2*S/3-a142	a61+a83-a60	2*S/3+a60-a61-a83	(13/3)*S-2*a72-a73-a74-a75-a76-a77-a78-a79-a80-a81-a82+a48-a49	a82	a81	a80	a79	a78	a77	a76	a75	a74	a73	a72	a49+a72-a48	a113+a114+a116+a115+a117+a118+a120+a119-a121+a110-a112-a123-a122-a124-5*S	(17/3)*S-a113-a114-a117-a118-a120-a119-a121-a110-a112-a123-a122-a124-5*S	2*S/3-a126	(2/3)*S+a94-a95-a126
a141	2*S/3-a141	a140+a139+a138+a137+a136+a135+a134+a133+a132+a131+a130+a129+a128+a127+2*a126-a94+a95-5*S	2*S/3-a140	2*S/3-a139	2*S/3-a138	2*S/3-a137	2*S/3-a136	2*S/3-a135	2*S/3-a134	2*S/3-a133	2*S/3-a132	2*S/3-a131	2*S/3-a130	2*S/3-a129	2*S/3-a128	2*S/3-a127	2*S/3-a126	2*S/3-a126	(2/3)*S+a94-a95-a126	
a111+a141-a110	(2/3)*S+a110-a111-a141	a138-a137-a136-a135-a134-a133-a132-a131-a130-a129-a128-a127-2*a126+a94-a95	a140	a139	a138	a137	a136	a135	a134	a133	a132	a131	a130	a129	a128	a127	a126	a126	a95+a126-a94	

• **Details**

It is an **algebraic cyclic-type** magic square of order 19 composed of four equal sums magic rectangles of orders 2×17 embedded with a magic square of order 15. It is again composed of four equal sums magic rectangles of order 2×13 and so on having a magic square of order 3 in the middle. In this case, the magic sums are $S_{3 \times 3} := S$, $S_{7 \times 7} := \frac{7S}{2}$, $S_{11 \times 11} := \frac{11S}{3}$, $S_{15 \times 15} := 5S$ and $S_{19 \times 19} := \frac{19S}{3}$. The width of magic rectangles is given as $m := \frac{2S}{3}$. In order to avoid decimal entries the magic sum of order 5 should be multiple of 5. Below are two examples.

Example 2.20. Let's consider following two examples based on the Result 2.20:

19	mgc	19x19																	1235		
		https://numbers-magic.com/ https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT																			
		281	284	287	290	293	296	299	302	305	308	311	314	317	320	323	326	-3751	-199	329	1235
		-151	-154	-157	-160	-163	-166	-169	-172	-175	-178	-181	-184	-187	-190	-193	-196	3881	-202	332	1235
		-5965	6095	143	146	149	152	155	158	161	164	167	170	173	176	-1069	-49	179	-205	335	1235
		464	-334	-13	-16	-19	-22	-25	-28	-31	-34	-37	-40	-43	-46	1199	-52	182	-208	338	1235
		461	-331	-2299	2429	50	53	56	59	62	65	68	71	101	56	74	-55	185	-211	341	1235
		458	-328	278	-148	80	77	74	71	68	65	62	59	29	53	77	-58	188	-214	344	1235
		455	-325	275	-145	-457	587	8	11	14	17	275	110	20	50	80	-61	191	-217	347	1235
		452	-322	272	-142	140	-10	122	119	116	113	-145	107	23	47	83	-64	194	-220	350	1235
		449	-319	269	-139	137	-7	149	-19	-58	125	128	104	26	44	86	-67	197	-223	353	1235
		446	-316	266	-136	134	-4	47	83	251	65	-121	101	29	41	89	-70	200	-226	356	1235
		443	-313	263	-133	131	-1	44	86	2	5	188	-97	227	38	92	-73	203	-229	359	1235
		440	-310	260	-130	128	2	41	89	-55	92	95	98	95	35	95	-76	206	-232	362	1235
		437	-307	257	-127	125	5	44	86	185	38	35	32	35	221	-91	-79	209	-235	365	1235
		434	-304	254	-124	122	8	395	14	17	20	23	26	29	32	29	-82	212	-238	368	1235
		431	-301	251	-121	125	5	-265	116	113	110	107	104	101	98	101	1631	-1501	-241	371	1235
		428	-298	248	-118	2033	-115	-112	-109	-106	-103	-100	-97	-94	-91	-88	-85	-88	-244	374	1235
		425	-295	251	-121	-1903	245	242	239	236	233	230	227	224	221	218	215	218	4649	-4519	1235
		422	-292	5375	-289	-286	-283	-280	-277	-274	-271	-268	-265	-262	-259	-256	-253	-250	-247	-250	1235
		425	-295	-5245	419	416	413	410	407	404	401	398	395	392	389	386	383	380	377	380	1235
		1235	1235	1235	1235	1235	1235	1235	1235	1235	1235	1235	1235	1235	1235	1235	1235	1235	1235	1235	1235

19	mgc	19x19																	1254
		https://numbers-magic.com/ https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT																	
281	284	287	290	293	296	299	302	305	308	311	314	317	320	323	326	-3734	-197	329	1254
-149	-152	-155	-158	-161	-164	-167	-170	-173	-176	-179	-182	-185	-188	-191	-194	3866	-200	332	1254
-5948	6080	143	146	149	152	155	158	161	164	167	170	173	176	-1056	-47	179	-203	335	1254
464	-332	-11	-14	-17	-20	-23	-26	-29	-32	-35	-38	-41	-44	1188	-50	182	-206	338	1254
461	-329	-2286	2418	50	53	56	59	62	65	68	71	110	58	74	-53	185	-209	341	1254
458	-326	278	-146	82	79	76	73	70	67	64	61	22	55	77	-56	188	-212	344	1254
455	-323	275	-143	-448	580	8	11	14	17	280	112	20	52	80	-59	191	-215	347	1254
452	-320	272	-140	140	-8	124	121	118	115	-148	109	23	49	83	-62	194	-218	350	1254
449	-317	269	-137	137	-5	154	-22	-59	127	130	106	26	46	86	-65	197	-221	353	1254
446	-314	266	-134	134	-2	47	85	255	66	-123	103	29	43	89	-68	200	-224	356	1254
443	-311	263	-131	131	1	44	88	2	5	191	-100	232	40	92	-71	203	-227	359	1254
440	-308	260	-128	128	4	41	91	-58	94	97	100	97	37	95	-74	206	-230	362	1254
437	-305	257	-125	125	7	44	88	190	38	35	32	35	214	-82	-77	209	-233	365	1254
434	-302	254	-122	122	10	388	16	19	22	25	28	31	34	31	-80	212	-236	368	1254
431	-299	251	-119	125	7	-256	116	113	110	107	104	101	98	101	1620	-1488	-239	371	1254
428	-296	248	-116	2022	-113	-110	-107	-104	-101	-98	-95	-92	-89	-86	-83	-86	-242	374	1254
425	-293	251	-119	-1890	245	242	239	236	233	230	227	224	221	218	215	218	4634	-4502	1254
422	-290	5360	-287	-284	-281	-278	-275	-272	-269	-266	-263	-260	-257	-254	-251	-248	-245	-248	1254
425	-293	-5228	419	416	413	410	407	404	401	398	395	392	389	386	383	380	377	380	1254
1254	1254	1254	1254	1254	1254	1254	1254	1254	1254	1254	1254	1254	1254	1254	1254	1254	1254	1254	1254

The magic sums are:

- **First example:** $S_{3 \times 3} := 195, S_{7 \times 7} := 455, S_{11 \times 11} := 715, S_{15 \times 15} := 975, S_{19 \times 19} := 1235$ and $m := 130$.
- **Second example:** $S_{3 \times 3} := 198, S_{7 \times 7} := 462, S_{11 \times 11} := 726, S_{15 \times 15} := 990, S_{19 \times 19} := 1254$ and $m := 132$.

2.8.2 Flat-Type

Result 2.21. Let's consider an algebraic magic square of order 19 with reduced entries:

a93	a94	a95	a96	a97	a98	a99	a100	a101	a102	a103	a104	a105	a106	a107	a108	(19/3)*S-a96-a95-a103-a102-a105-a104-a106-a101-a100-a108-a107-a109-a98-a99-a94-a93-a110-a97	a109	a110
2*S/3-a93	2*S/3-a94	2*S/3-a95	2*S/3-a96	2*S/3-a97	2*S/3-a98	2*S/3-a99	2*S/3-a100	2*S/3-a101	2*S/3-a102	2*S/3-a103	2*S/3-a104	2*S/3-a105	2*S/3-a106	2*S/3-a107	2*S/3-a108	a96+a95+a103+a102+a105+a104+a106+a101+a100+a108+a107+a109+a98+a99+a94+a93+a110+a97-(17/3)*S	2*S/3-a109	2*S/3-a110
5*S-a154-a153-a152-a151-a150-a149-a148-a147-a146-a145-a144-a143-a142-a141	a154+a153+a152+a151+a150+a149+a148+a147+a146+a145+a144+a143+a142+a141-(13/3)*S	a47	a48	a49	a50	a51	a52	a53	a54	a55	a56	a57	a58	5*S-a49-a48-a60-a51-a47-a52-a53-a54-a55-a56-a57-a58-a59-a50	a59	a60	2*S/3-a111	a111
a154	2*S/3-a154	(2/3)*S-a47	(2/3)*S-a48	(2/3)*S-a49	(2/3)*S-a50	(2/3)*S-a51	(2/3)*S-a52	(2/3)*S-a53	(2/3)*S-a54	(2/3)*S-a55	(2/3)*S-a56	(2/3)*S-a57	(2/3)*S-a58	a49+a48+a60+a51+a47+a52+a53+a54+a55+a56+a57+a58+a59+a50-(13/3)*S	(2/3)*S-a59	(2/3)*S-a60	2*S/3-a112	a112
a153	2*S/3-a153	(11/3)*S-a92-a91-a90-a89-a88-a87-a86-a85-a84-a83	a92+a91+a90+a89+a88+a87+a86+a85+a84+a83-3*S	a17	a18	a19	a20	a21	a22	a23	a24	(11/3)*S-a17-a18-a19-a20-a21-a22-a23-a24-a25-a26	a25	a26	(2/3)*S-a61	a61	2*S/3-a113	a113
a152	2*S/3-a152	a92	(2/3)*S-a92	(2/3)*S-a17	(2/3)*S-a18	(2/3)*S-a19	(2/3)*S-a20	(2/3)*S-a21	(2/3)*S-a22	(2/3)*S-a23	(2/3)*S-a24	a17+a18+a19+a20+a21+a22+a23+a24+a25+a26-3*S	(2/3)*S-a25	(2/3)*S-a26	(2/3)*S-a62	a62	2*S/3-a114	a114
a151	2*S/3-a151	a91	(2/3)*S-a91	(7/3)*S-a46-a45-a44-a43-a42-a41	a46+a45+a44+a43+a42+a41-(5/3)*S	a3	a4	a5	a6	(7/3)*S-a3-a4-a5-a6-a7-a8	a7	a8	(2/3)*S-a27	a27	(2/3)*S-a63	a63	2*S/3-a115	a115
a150	2*S/3-a150	a90	(2/3)*S-a90	a46	(2/3)*S-a46	(2/3)*S-a3	(2/3)*S-a4	(2/3)*S-a5	(2/3)*S-a6	a3+a4+a5+a6+a7+a8-(5/3)*S	(2/3)*S-a7	(2/3)*S-a8	(2/3)*S-a28	a28	(2/3)*S-a64	a64	2*S/3-a116	a116
a149	2*S/3-a149	a89	(2/3)*S-a89	a45	(2/3)*S-a45	5-a15-a16	a15+a16-(1/3)*S	a1+a2-S/3	2*S/3-a2	2*S/3-a1	(2/3)*S-a13	a13	(2/3)*S-a29	a29	(2/3)*S-a65	a65	2*S/3-a117	a117
a148	2*S/3-a148	a88	(2/3)*S-a88	a44	(2/3)*S-a44	a16	(2/3)*S-a16	4*S/3-2*a1-a2	S/3	2*a1+a2-2*S/3	(2/3)*S-a14	a14	(2/3)*S-a30	a30	(2/3)*S-a66	a66	2*S/3-a118	a118
a147	2*S/3-a147	a87	(2/3)*S-a87	a43	(2/3)*S-a43	a15	(2/3)*S-a15	a1	a2	5-a1-a2	a13+a14-(1/3)*S	5-a13-a14	(2/3)*S-a31	a31	(2/3)*S-a67	a67	2*S/3-a119	a119
a146	2*S/3-a146	a86	(2/3)*S-a86	a42	(2/3)*S-a42	(2/3)*S+a8-a7-a9	(2/3)*S-a9	a7+2*a9+a10+a11+2*a12-a3+a4-(5/3)*S-a8	(2/3)*S-a10	(2/3)*S-a11	(2/3)*S-a12	(2/3)*S+a3-a4-a12	(2/3)*S-a32	a32	(2/3)*S-a68	a68	2*S/3-a120	a120
a145	2*S/3-a145	a85	(2/3)*S-a85	a41	(2/3)*S-a41	a7+a9-a8	a9	(7/3)*S+a8-a7-2*a9-a10-a11-2*a12+a3-a4	a10	a11	a12	a4+a12-a3	a27+a28+a29+a30+a31+a32-(5/3)*S	(7/3)*S-a27-a28-a29-a30-a31-a32	(2/3)*S-a69	a69	2*S/3-a121	a121
a144	2*S/3-a144	a84	(2/3)*S-a84	(2/3)*S+a26-a25-a40	(2/3)*S-a40	a34+2*a33+a35+a36-a17+a37+a18+a38-a26+a25+2*a40+a39-3*S	(2/3)*S-a39	(2/3)*S-a38	(2/3)*S-a37	(2/3)*S-a36	(2/3)*S-a35	(2/3)*S-a34	(2/3)*S-a33	(2/3)*S+a17-a18-a33	(2/3)*S-a70	a70	2*S/3-a122	a122
a143	2*S/3-a143	a83	(2/3)*S-a83	a25+a40-a26	a40	(11/3)*S-a34-2*a33-a35-a36-a17-a37-a18-a38+a26-a25-2*a40-a39	a39	a38	a37	a36	a35	a34	a33	a18+a33-a17	a61+a62+a63+a64+a65+a66+a67+a68+a69+a70-3*S	(11/3)*S-a61-a62-a63-a64-a65-a66-a67-a68-a69-a70	2*S/3-a123	a123
a142	2*S/3-a142	(2/3)*S+a60-a59-a82	(2/3)*S-a82	a48+a78+a79+a72+a73-a60+a74+a81+a75+a76+a77+2*a71-a47+2*a82+a80+a59-(13/3)*S	(2/3)*S-a81	(2/3)*S-a80	(2/3)*S-a79	(2/3)*S-a78	(2/3)*S-a77	(2/3)*S-a76	(2/3)*S-a75	(2/3)*S-a74	(2/3)*S-a73	(2/3)*S-a72	(2/3)*S-a71	(2/3)*S+a47-a48-a71	2*S/3-a124	a124
a141	2*S/3-a141	a59+a82-a60	a82	5*S-a48-a78-a79-a72-a73+a60-a74-a81-a75-a76-a77-2*a71+a47-2*a82-a80-a59	a81	a80	a79	a78	a77	a76	a75	a74	a73	a72	a71	a48+a71-a47	a111+a112+a113+a114+a115+a116+a117+a118+a119+a120+a121+a122+a123+a124-(13/3)*S	5*S-a111-a112-a113-a114-a115-a116-a117-a118-a119-a120-a121-a122-a123-a124
(2/3)*S+a110-a109-a140	2*S/3-a140	a109+2*a140+a139+a138+a137+a136+a135+a134+a133+a132+a131+a130+a129+a128+a127+a126+2*a125+a94-a93-(17/3)*S-a110	2*S/3-a139	2*S/3-a138	2*S/3-a137	2*S/3-a136	2*S/3-a135	2*S/3-a134	2*S/3-a133	2*S/3-a132	2*S/3-a131	2*S/3-a130	2*S/3-a129	2*S/3-a128	2*S/3-a127	2*S/3-a126	2*S/3-a125	(2/3)*S+a93-a94-a125
a109+a140-a110	a140	(19/3)*S+a110-a109-2*a140-a139-a138-a137-a136-a135-a134-a133-a132-a131-a130-a129-a128-a127-a126-2*a125-a94+a93	a139	a138	a137	a136	a135	a134	a133	a132	a131	a130	a129	a128	a127	a126	a125	a94+a125-a93

• Details

It is an **algebraic flat-type** magic square of order 19 composed of two equal sums magic rectangles of orders 2×19 and two equal sums magic rectangles of order 2×15 embedded again with a **flat-type** magic square of order 15 and so on. In this case, the magic sums are $S_{3 \times 3} := S$, $S_{7 \times 7} := \frac{7S}{2}$, $S_{11 \times 11} := \frac{11S}{3}$, $S_{15 \times 15} := 5S$ and $S_{19 \times 19} := \frac{19S}{3}$. The width of magic rectangles is given as $m := \frac{2S}{3}$. In order to avoid decimal entries the magic sum of order 5 should be multiple of 5. Below are two examples.

Example 2.21. Let's consider following two examples based on the Result 2.21:

19	mgc	19x19 Inder J. Taneja https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT																	779	
	277	280	283	286	289	292	295	298	301	304	307	310	313	316	319	322	-4666	325	328	779
	-195	-198	-201	-204	-207	-210	-213	-216	-219	-222	-225	-228	-231	-234	-237	-240	4748	-243	-246	779
	-5552	5634	139	142	145	148	151	154	157	160	163	166	169	172	-1604	175	178	-249	331	779
	460	-378	-57	-60	-63	-66	-69	-72	-75	-78	-81	-84	-87	-90	1686	-93	-96	-252	334	779
	457	-375	-2154	2236	49	52	55	58	61	64	67	70	-174	73	76	-99	181	-255	337	779
	454	-372	274	-192	33	30	27	24	21	18	15	12	256	9	6	-102	184	-258	340	779
	451	-369	271	-189	-484	566	7	10	13	16	200	19	22	3	79	-105	187	-261	343	779
	448	-366	268	-186	136	-54	75	72	69	66	-118	63	60	0	82	-108	190	-264	346	779
	445	-363	265	-183	133	-51	34	48	-36	78	81	45	37	-3	85	-111	193	-267	349	779
	442	-360	262	-180	130	-48	46	36	158	41	-76	42	40	-6	88	-114	196	-270	352	779
	439	-357	259	-177	127	-45	43	39	1	4	118	36	46	-9	91	-117	199	-273	355	779
	436	-354	256	-174	124	-42	60	57	-28	54	51	48	45	-12	94	-120	202	-276	358	779
	433	-351	253	-171	121	-39	22	25	110	28	31	34	37	314	-232	-123	205	-279	361	779
	430	-348	250	-168	-33	-36	706	-33	-30	-27	-24	-21	-18	-15	-18	-126	208	-282	364	779
	427	-345	247	-165	115	118	-624	115	112	109	106	103	100	97	100	1576	-1494	-285	367	779
	424	-342	-159	-162	2652	-159	-156	-153	-150	-147	-144	-141	-138	-135	-132	-129	-132	-288	370	779
	421	-339	241	244	-2570	241	238	235	232	229	226	223	220	217	214	211	214	4374	-4292	779
	-333	-336	6422	-333	-330	-327	-324	-321	-318	-315	-312	-309	-306	-303	-300	-297	-294	-291	-294	779
	415	418	-6340	415	412	409	406	403	400	397	394	391	388	385	382	379	376	373	376	779
	779	779	779	779	779	779	779	779	779	779	779	779	779	779	779	779	779	779	779	779

19	mgc	19x19 Inder J. Taneja https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT																	1463	
	277	280	283	286	289	292	295	298	301	304	307	310	313	316	319	322	-3982	325	328	1463
	-123	-126	-129	-132	-135	-138	-141	-144	-147	-150	-153	-156	-159	-162	-165	-168	4136	-171	-174	1463
	-5012	5166	139	142	145	148	151	154	157	160	163	166	169	172	-1064	175	178	-177	331	1463
	460	-306	15	12	9	6	3	0	-3	-6	-9	-12	-15	-18	1218	-21	-24	-180	334	1463
	457	-303	-1758	1912	49	52	55	58	61	64	67	70	222	73	76	-27	181	-183	337	1463
	454	-300	274	-120	105	102	99	96	93	90	87	84	-68	81	78	-30	184	-186	340	1463
	451	-297	271	-117	-232	386	7	10	13	16	452	19	22	75	79	-33	187	-189	343	1463
	448	-294	268	-114	136	18	147	144	141	138	-298	135	132	72	82	-36	190	-192	346	1463
	445	-291	265	-111	133	21	142	12	-72	150	153	117	37	69	85	-39	193	-195	349	1463
	442	-288	262	-108	130	24	46	108	302	77	-148	114	40	66	88	-42	196	-198	352	1463
	439	-285	259	-105	127	27	43	111	1	4	226	0	154	63	91	-45	199	-201	355	1463
	436	-282	256	-102	124	30	132	129	-208	126	123	120	117	60	94	-48	202	-204	358	1463
	433	-279	253	-99	121	33	22	25	362	28	31	34	37	134	20	-51	205	-207	361	1463
	430	-276	250	-96	39	36	382	39	42	45	48	51	54	57	54	-54	208	-210	364	1463
	427	-273	247	-93	115	118	-228	115	112	109	106	103	100	97	100	1252	-1098	-213	367	1463
	424	-270	-87	-90	2184	-87	-84	-81	-78	-75	-72	-69	-66	-63	-60	-57	-60	-216	370	1463
	421	-267	241	244	-2030	241	238	235	232	229	226	223	220	217	214	211	214	3906	-3752	1463
	-261	-264	5810	-261	-258	-255	-252	-249	-246	-243	-240	-237	-234	-231	-228	-225	-222	-219	-222	1463
	415	418	-5656	415	412	409	406	403	400	397	394	391	388	385	382	379	376	373	376	1463
	1463	1463	1463	1463	1463	1463	1463	1463	1463	1463	1463	1463	1463	1463	1463	1463	1463	1463	1463	1463

The magic sums are:

- **First example:** $S_{3 \times 3} := 123, S_{7 \times 7} := 287, S_{11 \times 11} := 451, S_{15 \times 15} := 615, S_{19 \times 19} := 779$ and $m := 82$.
- **Second example:** $S_{3 \times 3} := 231, S_{7 \times 7} := 539, S_{11 \times 11} := 847, S_{15 \times 15} := 1155, S_{19 \times 19} := 1463$ and $m := 154$.

2.8.3 Cornered

Result 2.22. Let's consider an *algebraic magic square of order 19 with reduced entries*:

a1+a2-5/3	2 ⁵ /3-a2	2 ⁵ /3-a1	2 ⁵ /3-a3	a3	2 ⁵ /3-a7	a7	2 ⁵ /3-a15	a15	2 ⁵ /3-a27	a27	2 ⁵ /3-a43	a43	2 ⁵ /3-a63	a63	2 ⁵ /3-a87	a87	2 ⁵ /3-a115	a115			
4 ⁵ /3-2 ⁵ /3-a1-a2	5/3	2 ⁵ /3-a1-a2	2 ⁵ /3-a4	a4	2 ⁵ /3-a8	a8	2 ⁵ /3-a16	a16	2 ⁵ /3-a28	a28	2 ⁵ /3-a44	a44	2 ⁵ /3-a64	a64	2 ⁵ /3-a88	a88	2 ⁵ /3-a116	a116			
a1	a2	5-a1-a2	a3+a4-(1/3)*S	5-a3-a4	2 ⁵ /3-a9	a9	2 ⁵ /3-a17	a17	2 ⁵ /3-a29	a29	2 ⁵ /3-a45	a45	2 ⁵ /3-a65	a65	2 ⁵ /3-a89	a89	2 ⁵ /3-a117	a117			
(4/3)*S+a3-a4-a1-a2-a5	2 ⁵ /3-a5	a4+a1-a2+2 ⁵ /3+2 ⁵ /3-a6	2 ⁵ /3-a6	2 ⁵ /3-a6	2 ⁵ /3-a10	a10	2 ⁵ /3-a18	a18	2 ⁵ /3-a30	a30	2 ⁵ /3-a46	a46	2 ⁵ /3-a66	a66	2 ⁵ /3-a90	a90	2 ⁵ /3-a118	a118			
a4+a1+a2+a5-(2/3)*S-a3	a5	(7/3)*S+a3-a4-a1-a2-2 ⁵ /3-a6	a6	a6	a7+a8+a9+a10-5	(5/3)*S-a7-a8-a9-a10	2 ⁵ /3-a19	a19	2 ⁵ /3-a31	a31	2 ⁵ /3-a47	a47	2 ⁵ /3-a67	a67	2 ⁵ /3-a91	a91	2 ⁵ /3-a119	a119			
(11/3)*S+a7-a8-2 ⁵ /3-a1-a2-2 ⁵ /3-a11	2 ⁵ /3-a11	2 ⁵ /3-a12	2 ⁵ /3-a13	a8+2 ⁵ /3-a4+3 ⁵ /3-a6+a1+a2+2 ⁵ /3-a5+2 ⁵ /3-a11+a12+a13+2 ⁵ /3-a14-(14/3)*S-a7	2 ⁵ /3-a14	2 ⁵ /3-a14	2 ⁵ /3-a20	a20	2 ⁵ /3-a32	a32	2 ⁵ /3-a48	a48	2 ⁵ /3-a68	a68	2 ⁵ /3-a92	a92	2 ⁵ /3-a120	a120			
a8+2 ⁵ /3-a4+3 ⁵ /3-a6+a1+a2+2 ⁵ /3-a5+a11-3 ⁵ /3-a7	a11	a12	a13	(16/3)*S+a7-a8-2 ⁵ /3-a4-3 ⁵ /3-a6-a1-a2-2 ⁵ /3-a11-a12-a13-2 ⁵ /3-a14	a14	a14	a15+a16+a17+a18	(7/3)*S-a15-a16-a17-a18-a19-a20	2 ⁵ /3-a33	a33	2 ⁵ /3-a49	a49	2 ⁵ /3-a69	a69	2 ⁵ /3-a93	a93	2 ⁵ /3-a121	a121			
5+a15-a16+a9-a10+a6-a13+a12-a21	2 ⁵ /3-a21	2 ⁵ /3-a22	2 ⁵ /3-a23	2 ⁵ /3-a24	2 ⁵ /3-a25	a16-a9-a10-a6+a13-a12+2 ⁵ /3-a21+a22+a23+a24+a25+2 ⁵ /3-a26-(8/3)*S-a15	2 ⁵ /3-a26	2 ⁵ /3-a26	2 ⁵ /3-a34	a34	2 ⁵ /3-a50	a50	2 ⁵ /3-a70	a70	2 ⁵ /3-a94	a94	2 ⁵ /3-a122	a122			
a16-a9-a10-a6+a13-a12+a21-(1/3)*S-a15	a21	a22	a23	a24	a25	(10/3)*S+a15-a16+a9-a10+a6-a13+a12-2 ⁵ /3-a21-a22-a23-a24-a25-2 ⁵ /3-a26	a26	a26	a27+a28+a29+a30+a31+a32+a33+a34-4*(7/3)*S	3 ⁵ /3-a27-a28-a29-a30-a31-a32-a33-a34	2 ⁵ /3-a51	a51	2 ⁵ /3-a71	a71	2 ⁵ /3-a95	a95	2 ⁵ /3-a123	a123			
(22/3)*S+a22-3 ⁵ /3-a14-a35-2 ⁵ /3-a11-a10+a17-a12-a9-a18-a12-a1-a2-a23-2 ⁵ /3-a8-a28-3 ⁵ /3-a6+a27-2 ⁵ /3-a4	2 ⁵ /3-a35	2 ⁵ /3-a36	2 ⁵ /3-a37	2 ⁵ /3-a38	2 ⁵ /3-a39	2 ⁵ /3-a40	2 ⁵ /3-a41	2 ⁵ /3-a41	2 ⁵ /3-a42	2 ⁵ /3-a42	2 ⁵ /3-a52	a52	2 ⁵ /3-a72	a72	2 ⁵ /3-a96	a96	2 ⁵ /3-a124	a124			
3 ⁵ /3-a14+a35+2 ⁵ /3-a11-a10-a17+a13+a9+a18+a12+a1+a2+a23+2 ⁵ /3-a8+a28+3 ⁵ /3-a6+a27+2 ⁵ /3-a4-(20/3)*S+a39-a22	a35	a36	a37	a38	a39	a40	a41	a41	a42	a42	a43+a44+a45+a46+a47+a48+a49+a50+a51+a52-3 ⁵ /3	(11/3)*S-a43-a44-a45-a46-a47-a48-a49-a50-a51-a52	2 ⁵ /3-a73	a73	2 ⁵ /3-a97	a97	2 ⁵ /3-a125	a125			
(1/3)*S+a43-a44+a29-a30+a19-a20+a14-a25+a24-a37+a36-a53	2 ⁵ /3-a53	2 ⁵ /3-a54	2 ⁵ /3-a55	2 ⁵ /3-a56	2 ⁵ /3-a57	2 ⁵ /3-a58	2 ⁵ /3-a59	2 ⁵ /3-a60	2 ⁵ /3-a61	2 ⁵ /3-a61	a44+2 ⁵ /3-a62+a61+a60+a59+a58+a57+a56+a55+a54+2 ⁵ /3-a53-a36+a37+a20-a14-a19+a30-a29+a25-a24-(10/3)*S-a43	2 ⁵ /3-a62	2 ⁵ /3-a62	2 ⁵ /3-a74	a74	2 ⁵ /3-a98	a98	2 ⁵ /3-a126	a126		
(1/3)*S-a43+a44-a29+a30-a19-a20-a14+a25-a24+a37-a36+a53	a53	a54	a55	a56	a57	a58	a59	a60	a61	a61	4 ⁵ /3+a43-a44-2 ⁵ /3-a62-a61-a60-a59-a58-a57-a56-a55-a54-2 ⁵ /3-a53+a36-a37-a20-a14+a19-a30+a29-a25-a24	2 ⁵ /3-a62	a62	a63+a64+a65+a66+a67+a68+a69+a70+a71+a72+a73+a74-(11/3)*S	(13/3)*S-a63-a64-a65-a66-a67-a68-a69	2 ⁵ /3-a99	a99	2 ⁵ /3-a127	a127		
6 ⁵ /3-a75-a55+a54+a38-a39-a23-a24-a25+a12-2 ⁵ /3-a21-a22-a9-a10-a13-3 ⁵ /3-a26-a20-2 ⁵ /3-a16-a17-a18-a19-a32+a31+a45-a46+a6-a64+a63	2 ⁵ /3-a75	2 ⁵ /3-a76	2 ⁵ /3-a77	2 ⁵ /3-a78	2 ⁵ /3-a79	2 ⁵ /3-a80	2 ⁵ /3-a81	2 ⁵ /3-a82	2 ⁵ /3-a83	2 ⁵ /3-a84	2 ⁵ /3-a85	2 ⁵ /3-a86	2 ⁵ /3-a86	2 ⁵ /3-a100	a100	2 ⁵ /3-a128	a128				
a75+a55-a54-a38+a39+a23+a24+a25-a12+2 ⁵ /3-a21-a22-a9-a10-a13+3 ⁵ /3-a26+a20+2 ⁵ /3-a16+a17+a18+a19+a32-a31-a45-a46-a6+a64-a63-(16/3)*S	a75	a76	a77	a78	a79	a80	a81	a82	a83	a84	a85	a86	a86	a87+a88+a89+a90+a91+a92+a93+a94+a95+a96+a97+a98+a99+a100-(13/3)*S	5 ⁵ /3-a87-a88-a89-a90-a91-a92-a93-a94-a95-a96-a97-a98-a99-a100	2 ⁵ /3-a129	a129				
(1/3)*S-a77-a76-a88-a87-a57-a56-a40-a41-a34-a48+a33+a47+a26-a101-a66+a65	2 ⁵ /3-a101	2 ⁵ /3-a102	2 ⁵ /3-a103	2 ⁵ /3-a104	2 ⁵ /3-a105	2 ⁵ /3-a106	2 ⁵ /3-a107	2 ⁵ /3-a108	2 ⁵ /3-a109	2 ⁵ /3-a110	2 ⁵ /3-a111	2 ⁵ /3-a112	2 ⁵ /3-a113	2 ⁵ /3-a113	a77+a111+a112+a113-a76+a88+2 ⁵ /3-a114-a107-a108-a87+a57-a56-a40-a41-a34-a48-a33-a47-a26+a109+a110+2 ⁵ /3-a101-(14/3)*S-a66-a65+a105+a106+a103+a104	2 ⁵ /3-a114	2 ⁵ /3-a114	2 ⁵ /3-a130	a130		
(1/3)*S-a77-a76-a88-a87-a57-a56-a40-a41-a34-a48+a33+a47-a26+a101+a66-a65	a101	a102	a103	a104	a105	a106	a107	a108	a109	a110	a111	a112	a113	a113	a76-a88-2 ⁵ /3-a114-a107-a108-a87-a57+a56+a40-a41-a34-a48+a33+a47+a26-a109-a110-2 ⁵ /3-a101+(16/3)*S-a66+a65-a105-a106-a103-a104-a77-a111-a112-a113	2 ⁵ /3-a114	a114	a116+a117+a118+a119+a120+a121+a122+a123+a124+a125+a126+a127+a128+a129+a130-5 ⁵ /3+a115	(7/3)*S-a115-a116-a117-a118-a119-a120-a121-a122-a123-a124-a125-a126-a127-a128-a129-a130	2 ⁵ /3-a130	a130
a78+a89-a90-2 ⁵ /3-a5-2 ⁵ /3-a116+a115-a50+a49+a58-a40-a41-a34-a33-a38-a39-a23-a12-a22-a9-a10-a13-a17-a18-a32-a31-a59-a102-a1-a2-a37-a131-3 ⁵ /3-a6-2 ⁵ /3-a11-2 ⁵ /3-a35-a36-3 ⁵ /3-a14-(41/3)*S-a67-a68-a103-2 ⁵ /3-a8-3 ⁵ /3-a42-2 ⁵ /3-a28-a29-a30-a79	2 ⁵ /3-a131	2 ⁵ /3-a132	2 ⁵ /3-a133	2 ⁵ /3-a134	2 ⁵ /3-a135	2 ⁵ /3-a136	2 ⁵ /3-a137	2 ⁵ /3-a138	2 ⁵ /3-a139	2 ⁵ /3-a140	2 ⁵ /3-a141	2 ⁵ /3-a142	2 ⁵ /3-a143	2 ⁵ /3-a144	2 ⁵ /3-a145	2 ⁵ /3-a146	2 ⁵ /3-a146	2 ⁵ /3-a146			
2 ⁵ /3-a131	a131	a132	a133	a134	a135	a136	a137	a138	a139	a140	a141	a142	a143	a144	a145	a146	a146	a146			

• **Details**

It is an **algebraic cornered**, where the magic squares of orders 19, where the magic squares of order 3, 5, 7, 9, 11, 13, 15 and 17 are at the upper-left corner. In this case, the magic sums are $S_{3 \times 3} := S$, $S_{5 \times 5} := \frac{5S}{3}$, $S_{7 \times 7} := \frac{7S}{3}$, $S_{9 \times 9} := 3S$, $S_{11 \times 11} := \frac{11S}{3}$, $S_{13 \times 13} := \frac{13S}{3}$, $S_{15 \times 15} := 5S$, $S_{17 \times 17} := \frac{17S}{3}$ and $S_{19 \times 19} := \frac{19S}{3}$. The width of magic rectangles is given as $m := \frac{2S}{3}$. In order to avoid decimal entries the magic sum of order 3 should be multiple of 3. Below are two examples.

Example 2.22. Let's consider following two examples based on the Result 2.22:

19	mgc	19x19 Inder J. Taneja https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT																		931
	-46	96	97	95	3	91	7	83	15	71	27	55	43	35	63	11	87	-17	115	931
	192	49	-94	94	4	90	8	82	16	70	28	54	44	34	64	10	88	-18	116	931
	1	2	144	-42	140	89	9	81	17	69	29	53	45	33	65	9	89	-19	117	931
	187	93	-219	92	92	88	10	80	18	68	30	52	46	32	66	8	90	-20	118	931
	-89	5	317	6	6	-113	211	79	19	67	31	51	47	31	67	7	91	-21	119	931
	488	87	86	85	-571	84	84	78	20	66	32	50	48	30	68	6	92	-22	120	931
	-390	11	12	13	669	14	14	-140	238	65	33	49	49	29	69	5	93	-23	121	931
	129	77	76	75	74	73	-207	72	72	64	34	48	50	28	70	4	94	-24	122	931
	-31	21	22	23	24	25	305	26	26	-99	197	47	51	27	71	3	95	-25	123	931
	877	63	62	61	60	59	58	57	-870	56	56	46	52	26	72	2	96	-26	124	931
	-779	35	36	37	38	39	40	41	968	42	42	34	64	25	73	1	97	-27	125	931
	5	45	44	43	42	41	40	39	38	37	191	36	36	24	74	0	98	-28	126	931
	93	53	54	55	56	57	58	59	60	61	-93	62	62	283	-185	-1	99	-29	127	931
	486	23	22	21	20	19	18	17	16	15	14	13	27	12	12	-2	100	-30	128	931
	-388	75	76	77	78	79	80	81	82	83	84	85	71	86	86	672	-574	-31	129	931
	-33	-3	-4	-5	-6	-7	-8	-9	-10	-11	-12	-13	-14	-15	1015	-16	-16	-32	130	931
	131	101	102	103	104	105	106	107	108	109	110	111	112	113	-917	114	114	1225	-1127	931
	1034	-33	-34	-35	-36	-37	-38	-39	-40	-41	-42	-43	-44	-45	-46	-47	593	-48	-48	931
	-936	131	132	133	134	135	136	137	138	139	140	141	142	143	144	145	-495	146	146	931
	931	931	931	931	931	931	931	931	931	931	931	931	931	931	931	931	931	931	931	931

19	mgc	19x19 Inder J. Taneja https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT																836		
-41	86	87	85	3	81	7	73	15	61	27	45	43	25	63	1	87	-27	115	836	
172	44	-84	84	4	80	8	72	16	60	28	44	44	24	64	0	88	-28	116	836	
1	2	129	-37	125	79	9	71	17	59	29	43	45	23	65	-1	89	-29	117	836	
167	83	-194	82	82	78	10	70	18	58	30	42	46	22	66	-2	90	-30	118	836	
-79	5	282	6	6	-98	186	69	19	57	31	41	47	21	67	-3	91	-31	119	836	
433	77	76	75	-501	74	74	68	20	56	32	40	48	20	68	-4	92	-32	120	836	
-345	11	12	13	589	14	14	-115	203	55	33	39	49	19	69	-5	93	-33	121	836	
114	67	66	65	64	63	-167	62	62	54	34	38	50	18	70	-6	94	-34	122	836	
-26	21	22	23	24	25	255	26	26	-64	152	37	51	17	71	-7	95	-35	123	836	
767	53	52	51	50	49	48	47	-725	46	46	36	52	16	72	-8	96	-36	124	836	
-679	35	36	37	38	39	40	41	813	42	42	79	9	15	73	-9	97	-37	125	836	
0	35	34	33	32	31	30	29	28	27	241	26	26	14	74	-10	98	-38	126	836	
88	53	54	55	56	57	58	59	60	61	-153	62	62	338	-250	-11	99	-39	127	836	
396	13	12	11	10	9	8	7	6	5	4	3	172	2	2	-12	100	-40	128	836	
-308	75	76	77	78	79	80	81	82	83	84	85	-84	86	86	737	-649	-41	129	836	
-38	-13	-14	-15	-16	-17	-18	-19	-20	-21	-22	-23	-24	-25	1085	-26	-26	-42	130	836	
126	101	102	103	104	105	106	107	108	109	110	111	112	113	-997	114	114	1300	-1212	836	
829	-43	-44	-45	-46	-47	-48	-49	-50	-51	-52	-53	-54	-55	-56	-57	873	-58	-58	836	
-741	131	132	133	134	135	136	137	138	139	140	141	142	143	144	145	-785	146	146	836	
836	836	836	836	836	836	836	836	836	836	836	836	836	836	836	836	836	836	836	836	836

The magic sums are:

- **First example:** $S_{3 \times 3} := 147, S_{5 \times 5} := 245, S_{7 \times 7} := 343, S_{9 \times 9} := 441, S_{11 \times 11} := 539, S_{13 \times 13} := 637, S_{15 \times 15} := 735, S_{17 \times 17} := 833, S_{19 \times 19} := 931$ and $m := 98$.
- **Second example:** $S_{3 \times 3} := 132, S_{5 \times 5} := 220, S_{7 \times 7} := 308, S_{9 \times 9} := 396, S_{11 \times 11} := 484, S_{13 \times 13} := 572, S_{15 \times 15} := 660, S_{17 \times 17} := 748, S_{19 \times 19} := 836$ and $m := 88$.

3 Author's Contribution to Magic Squares and Recreation of Numbers

For author's contribution to **magic squares** and **recreation of numbers** please see the links below:

- **Inder J. Taneja, Magic Squares,**
 - (i) <https://numbers-magic.com/?p=668>
 - (ii) <https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/2019/06/27/publications-magic-squares/>
- **Inder J. Taneja, Recreation of Numbers,**
 - (i) <https://numbers-magic.com/?p=671>
 - (ii) <https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/2019/06/27/publications-recreation-of-numbers/>

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- [3] **F. Gaspalou**, "Magic Squares" <http://www.gaspalou.fr/magic-squares/>
- [4] **W. Trump**, <http://www.trump.de/magic-squares>
- [5] **H. White**, Bordered Magic Squares - <http://budshaw.ca/Download.html>
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- **Algebraic Magic Squares: Dates and Days of the Year**

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- **Algebraic Magic Squares: Different Styles**

- **Algebraic Magic Squares: Different Styles**

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• Double-Digit Magic Squares

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• Cornered Magic Squares

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